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RESISTIRÉ

Reducing gendered inequalities
caused by COVID-19 policies

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Report on solutions cycle 1

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The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of its author and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.

List of acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
EU-27	European Union (27 countries)
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GIA	Gender Impact Assessment
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
RAS	Rapid Assessment Survey
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
WP	Work Package

Summary

The aim of RESISTIRÉ is to understand the unequal impacts of the COVID-19 outbreak and its policy responses on behavioural, social and economic inequalities in 31 countries (EU-27 plus Iceland, UK, Serbia and Turkey) and to work towards individual and societal resilience. It does so by mapping policies and social initiatives on the one hand, and collecting quantitative and qualitative data on the other, and by analysing and translating these to insights to be used for designing, devising and piloting solutions for improved policies and social innovations to be deployed by policymakers, stakeholders and actors in the field in different policy domains. The project relies on a ten-partner multidisciplinary and multisectoral European consortium, and a well-established network of researchers in 31 countries.

This report gives an overview of the further development of the action-ideas that came out of the Open Studios³ and how they were further combined with results of the research activities of the first cycle. They have been developed into Operational Recommendations, Pilot Projects and an Agenda for Future Research⁴.

The Operational Recommendations, designed as RESISTIRÉ Factsheets, focus on eight topics: gender mainstreaming, gender-balanced decision-making, a gender equality and diversity plan for hospitals, inclusive green spaces/commons, care and work-life balance, gender-based violence (on the European level and the national/local level), and telework. The Factsheets provide a brief overview of how COVID-19 has made visible or reinforced existing inequalities in the concerning theme, show personal stories of people affected by them, and give examples of inspiring policies to mitigate these inequalities. Finally, the Factsheets list several policy recommendations that would address the inequalities.

The Pilot Projects are a selection of three action-ideas, that have been developed into project concepts that would address some of the inequalities that RESISTIRÉ has researched. The three selected project concepts are Employers Who Care, Green Spaces as Caring Ecosystems, and the Caring Workspaces. These project concepts have been designed and refined based on the input of the Open Studios, as well as other experts knowledgeable on the topic. A public call will be launched, whereby interested organisations can apply to lead the project.

Finally, the Agenda for Future Research consists of four domains, which contain an analysis of previous findings from the RESISTIRÉ project, as well as an identification of research

³ For more information about the Open Studios, please refer to D5.2 ([HERE](#))

⁴ Some outputs reported in this deliverable may be modified slightly after the publishing of this document, to further improve its quality and effectiveness.

gaps. It also outlines which research questions and topics future research should address, and what questions RESISTIRÉ will focus on in the second cycle.

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Introduction

The aim of RESISTIRÉ is to understand the unequal impacts of the COVID-19 outbreak and its policy responses on behavioural, social and economic inequalities in 31 countries (EU-27 plus Iceland, UK, Serbia and Turkey) and to work towards individual and societal resilience. The pandemic has led to the introduction of national policy responses and measures in multiple policy domains to slow infections, prevent deaths and to address some of the socio-economic issues emerged (Cibin et al., 2021). These measures have profoundly changed lives, with physical and social distancing becoming the new norm and, where needed, quarantining and self-isolation. They have radically shifted how society is organised, with increased working from home, home-schooling and intensification of online presence, all with their own specific (un)intended consequences (Axelsson et al., 2021; Bonaccorsi et al., 2020). This new policy framework has also meant furloughing and job losses, with associated economic hardship and mental health issues, and delayed ordinary health treatments (Nicola et al., 2020; Van Bavel, 2020; Lewnard & Lo, 2020). And it has meant increases in the levels of gender-based violence and variations in access to support and healthcare.

The impacts of these developments, like those of other crises, are gendered and related to sex, age, disability, ethnicity/race, migration status, religion, social class, and the intersections between these inequalities (Lokot & Avakyan, 2020; Walter & McGregor, 2020; Walby, 2015). The impacts are uneven and unequal, disproportional in their consequences for different groups, and their long-term impacts are uncertain (Cumming et al., 2020). Women have been disproportionately infected by COVID-19 (Sciensano, 2020) and affected by its impact; as front-line workers, as formal or informal caregivers in society; as exposed to a higher risk of men's violence, in particular as victims of intimate partner violence. As these positions intersect with social class, ethnicity, age and other inequalities, we deploy a 'gender+' approach, which highlights and builds on gender relations and gender inequalities, but always considering how these intersect with other complex inequalities (Verloo, 2013; Walby et al., 2012). RESISTIRÉ helps to understand how different policy responses are having unequal effects, but also how different responses can be put into place to understand and address gender and intersectional inequalities in different policy domains (Lombardo & Kantola, 2019).

To meet these aims, RESISTIRÉ conducts policy analysis, as well as quantitative and qualitative research activities, to inform the design of innovative solutions. In this way, it responds to the outbreak through co-created and inclusive strategies that address old and new, durable and temporary inequality patterns in and across policy domains. The overall methodology of RESISTIRÉ is based on a step-by-step process running in three cycles over 24 months (April 2021/March 2023). All project activities are organised in these

three cycles, feeding results into one another (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: RESISTIRÉ methodological step-by-step three cycle process

This report provides an overview of the concrete outputs that have been developed in the first cycle of the RESISTIRÉ process for different target groups, namely policymakers; civil society; employers; the research community at large including research funding organisations (RFOs) and other stakeholders based on the preceding research phase (WP2-4) and the Open Studios (WP5).

The outputs are the result of three activities running in parallel. First, the development of Operational Recommendations for policymakers and other stakeholders. Recommendations have been developed and will be presented as Factsheets to different types of policymakers (EU, national, regional, local levels) and for different types of stakeholders (CSO, NGO's, employers). Second, the development and launch of Pilot Projects. Ideas that came out of the Open Studios have been developed into concrete actions (objective, target group, approach, impacts). Three of these actions have been developed in order to launch a pilot (prototyping the action). Third, the systematic monitoring of the analyses of quantitative and qualitative data in each cycle and the development of the Agenda for Future Research to collect knowledge gaps as identified in the Open Studios. These gaps will be gathered in a living repository accessible by all partners involved.

The next chapter provides more information on the Operational Recommendations. In a following chapter, the selected Pilot Projects are covered. Another chapter will then describe the Agenda for Future Research. We end this report with conclusions.

Operational Recommendations

To begin, this chapter describes the process that produced and refined the eight Factsheets containing policy recommendations guidelines. Afterwards, a more in-depth description of each individual fact sheet is given as they were produced in Task 6.1.

The development of the recommendations started with an analysis of the results of the research phase (WP2-4) to find solutions to the issues that were identified. This resulted in the elaboration of three initial Factsheets concerning gender mainstreaming, gender-balanced decision-making, and gender-based violence. The Open Studios (WP5) of the first cycle contributed to this process by proposing an additional three solutions that grew out of the co-created ideas for action coming out of each Open Studio. In identifying and further concretising these recommendations, care was taken to ensure that they had an innovative nature, that they could have a real impact, and that there was a balanced approach between different subjects and target groups.

The initial six documents were put into the form of Factsheets that included a number of sections to provide, among other details, further background information, main findings from the RESISTIRÉ project, promising practices among policies and societal initiatives, potential target groups, and the concrete recommendations themselves. This was initially done by one person (designated as the lead) per fact sheet. These Factsheets were then shared with all of the consortium partners, who, based on their professional experience and on their findings from the project, were asked to add any comments, suggestions, and additions that they deemed necessary in order to make the proposed recommendations more comprehensive. These changes and annotations were subsequently incorporated into the Factsheets by the leads, supported by a core group of contributors from the partners who engaged to support the lead.

To assess and refine the resulting Factsheets further, a workshop was organised that brought together experts from inside and outside of the consortium (see Table 1 below) with specific expertise on the topics covered. At least one invited participant per fact sheet topic had specialised knowledge on the topic at hand.

Table 1 – List of Workshop Participants

Invited Participants	Consortium Participants	Consortium Participants (continued)
Julian Siravo (Autonomy UK)	Aart Kerremans (YW)	Igor Živković (YW)
Ileana Aiese (BeFree Cooperativa)	Adam Brandstetter-Kunc (ESF)	Lorenzo Lionello (Sciensano)
Izaskun Bernal (Coach & Consultant)	Alain Denis (YW)	Marcela Linková (ISAS)
Marie Trollvik (Lönelotsarna)	Alicja Bobek (TU Dublin)	María López Beloso (UDEUSTO)
Murat Güney (Istanbul Planning Agency)	Anne-Charlott Callerstig (ORU)	Marina Cacace (K&I)
Paula Franklin (European Trade Union Institute)	Ayşe Gül Altınay (SU)	Nazlı Türker (SU)
	Clare Stovell (OBU)	Roberto Cibirin (ISAS)
	Elaheh Mohammadi (ISAS)	Selin Nugent (OBU)

The workshop was held online over three hours using a combination of Zoom and Miro, an online whiteboard which was used to adequately capture the participants' feedback. The workshop was divided into two parts, with each part covering three of the six proposed Factsheets and the experts working concurrently in three smaller groups.

Before the beginning of the workshop, the experts had received access to the six Factsheets and, during the workshop and in small groups, they were able to (re)read the recommendations. After everyone had familiarised themselves with the documents, they were asked to provide their initial spontaneous reactions to the recommendations and to think about what the main message of the recommendation should ideally be (and what title would fit this message). Next, the participants reflected on whether the content of the recommendations was in line with this main message, whether some aspects needed to be altered or strengthened, and if the provided context (background info, examples, ...) was sufficient to understand the situation or if it missed crucial information. Afterwards, the participants were asked to think of what target groups the recommendations should address, of ways to reach these target groups, and of the specific actions that were needed to integrate all of this feedback into the final fact sheet. Finally, the participants briefly returned to the plenary meeting to discuss their findings with the other groups and to elicit additional comments.

The feedback and input of the experts were taken into account by the leads and supporting contributors in numerous ways when developing the Factsheets with more in-depth recommendations and altering them where necessary. For example, the fact sheet on 'Care' was split into two, with one part focusing on the topic of care work and the other

part on the topic of telework. The same happened with the document on gender-based violence, which was divided into a set of recommendations for policymakers at the European level on the one hand and recommendations for national and local policymakers on the other. This brought the number of documents to a total of eight. A lot of the substance of the initial recommendations was expanded and/or altered as well thanks to the feedback collected through the workshop.

Finally, a last review of each fact sheet was carried out by partners from the consortium and by external experts to finalise the recommendations and ensure their readiness for communication and dissemination to the identified target groups.

Below, the eight Factsheets are laid out in more detail, with each one centred around a distinct topic and target group(s), as indicated in Table 2 below. A title for each fact sheet is also indicated in the table.

Table 2 – Operational Recommendations

Topic	Title	Target Group(s)
Gender Mainstreaming	Amnesia, the side-effect of COVID-19. Decades of work towards intersectional gender mainstreaming wiped out during the crisis!	Policymakers
Gender-balanced Decision-making	Ensuring gender-balanced decision-making and the involvement of civil society	Policymakers and CSOs
Gender Equality and Diversity Plan for Hospitals	Gender Equality Plans should be mandatory for hospitals	Employers (hospitals) and policymakers
Inclusive Green Spaces/Commons	Green for Everyone. Promoting Green Spaces and Mitigating Gentrification	Policymakers, CSOs and employers
Care	Care and Crisis: Fostering a Paradigm Shift	Employers and policymakers
Gender-based Violence (European Level)	Reinforcing EU level action to combat gender-based violence through the Istanbul Convention	Policymakers
Gender-based Violence (National & Local Level)	Improving national responses to gender-based violence: lessons from the pandemic crisis	Policymakers
Telework	Telework as a Double-edged	Employers and

	Sword: Risks and Opportunities	policy-makers
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There has been a common approach to the structure of the eight Factsheets, but adaptations have been carried out according to the specific subject matter and target group(s). Therefore, while they have a similar structure, there are notable differences between each one. Moreover, the documents were strengthened through the use of visual materials (i.e., infographics), with each fact sheet going through a process of identifying the most appropriate messages/content for visualisation and, subsequently, developing and integrating those visuals.

Amnesia, the side-effect of COVID-19. Decades of work towards intersectional gender mainstreaming wiped out during the crisis

Although gender mainstreaming has been adopted as an approach in EU policymaking for over two decades, national-level policies are largely still not mainstreamed. Gender mainstreaming should not only be an ambition, it should also be implemented, monitored, and evaluated, with concrete results and impact. In particular, policies should not only focus on so-called “traditional” or “typical” family models, citizenship criteria, and standard employment contracts, as this focus results in the exclusion of large segments of European societies (e.g., LGBTQI+ people, the unemployed, migrants etc.).

› *Background information*

The need to provide rapid responses in times of crisis often overshadows the consideration of gender inequality issues when designing policies to deal with such situations. For instance, taking an example from the recent past, the European Institute for Gender Equality underlines how “fiscal measures adopted in the wake of the 2008 financial crisis had a disproportionately negative impact on women”, stressing that “this should be avoided in COVID-19 recovery measures.”¹ **Compounded by other grounds of inequality** (such as sexual orientation, ethnicity, socioeconomic background and disabilities, to name a few), turning a blind eye to gender inequalities in the policies related to the pandemic means leaving behind a considerable population in the EU.

GENDER EQUALITY & ECONOMIC IMPACT

Figure 1: Global GDP cost by 2030 of a lack of intervention on the pandemic and its economic fallout's regressive effect on gender equality and employment (based on the McKinsey & Company's report cited on the text)

A [report](#)² from McKinsey & Company estimated that a lack of intervention on the pandemic and its economic fallout's regressive effect on gender equality and employment would cost at least \$1 trillion global GDP growth in 2030 (Figure 1). "Conversely, taking action now to advance gender equality could be valuable, adding \$13 trillion to global GDP in 2030 compared with the gender-regressive scenario."

➤ Policy mapping: main findings

RESISTIRÉ analyses show that although gender mainstreaming has been adopted as an approach in EU policymaking for over two decades, **policies to combat COVID-19 have been largely not gender mainstreamed at the national level.** For instance, out of a total of 298 policies analysed (Figure 2):

COVID POLICIES IN EUROPE

Has a Gender Impact Assessment
been carried out?

Figure 2: Percentage of policies related to COVID-19 gender+ inequality domains subjected to Gender Impact Assessment (Sample of 298 policies belonging to EU27 countries (excluding Estonia and Malta) along with Iceland, the UK, Serbia, and Turkey) (Cibin et al., 2021)

- for only 2% of the policies a Gender Impact Assessment (GIA) has been carried out
- in 58% of the cases, the GIA has not been carried out at all, and for the 40% of the cases there was no ground to assess this.

In addition, as the majority of the national reports underline, most of the policies that were introduced to manage the pandemic **did not take into account aspects related to gender inequalities and other intersecting vulnerability grounds**. This lack was especially pronounced in, but not limited to, the first phase of the pandemic. The UN COVID-19 Global Gender Response Tracker³, a project to monitor responses taken by governments worldwide to tackle the pandemic, reports that in Europe **only 30% of the identified measures can be considered gender-sensitive**.

The RESISTIRÉ project also mapped quantitative, comparative information on indicators that allow to measure and monitor the economic, social and environmental impacts of COVID-19. While evidence provides a clear picture of some inequalities in Europe, a detailed analysis was not possible for all the domains due to data unavailability. This highlights the need for **comparable and harmonised data at the European level on the gender pay gap, gender-based violence, decision making and environmental justice**. Importantly, existing data is particularly limited for the most marginalised groups in **society**, and current analyses rarely extend beyond differences in socioeconomic status, family structure and education. **Non-registered workers, migrants, refugees and the homeless** are likely to have been severely affected by COVID-19 and related government restrictions, however, little evidence is available to assess these impacts across the domains of interest. In addition, existing analysis of available data often did not include

gendered/intersectional analysis, even if gender and other variables were available.

› *Expert consultations: main findings*

- Gender inequalities in this domain are illustrated by both the absence of women in decision-making and of women’s voices in explaining the pandemic to society.
- The experts agree that this absence of women in leadership, decision-making and political participation and the invisibility of their voices during the crisis can be explained by traditional gender stereotypes portraying males as leaders.
- During the pandemic, emphasis has been put on rapid decision-making by homogeneous (not diverse) teams and privileged individuals who tend to be older white men in European societies, while inclusive decision-making has been treated as less adequate given the exceptional circumstances and therefore less legitimate. This exclusionary leadership style means that the voice of women who were previously in leadership teams is now absent.
- The experts affirm that “full gender leadership is not represented yet” and argue for more diversity among politicians which would result in more inclusive and intersectional policies.
- The experts also emphasise that civil society groups are in a strong position to amplify highly marginalised voices. They should be consulted for policy design.

› *Better Stories*

Within RESISTIRE, we identify “Better Stories”, a term taken from Dina Georgis (2013) for promising practices that identify how a given societal situation can be ameliorated to improve existing practices.

Policies: “Better stories” from Spain and Portugal

In the analysis conducted within the RESISTIRÉ project, several policies were identified in which attention was paid to specific gender dynamics.

In Spain, for instance, the “Urgent measures for the protection and assistance to victims of gender-based violence (Law 1/2021)” addressed the special vulnerability of women victims of GBV and trafficking due to the policies enforced in relation to COVID-19. It considered GBV as a threat to human rights, which needs to be tackled by guaranteeing access to integrated social assistance.

The law aimed at maintaining and adapting existing services (integrated assistance and protection services) to ensure their functioning during the pandemic, establishing organisational measures as well as adaptation of the modes of provision.

To this end, such services were declared essential and the law explicitly states that these services shall be guaranteed to all women, “regardless their ethnicity, socio-economic level, age, migrant status, functional diversity, disability, dependency, place of residence and any other situation” amounting to **intersectional** discrimination. The law makes specific reference to women with disability and women living in rural areas and the barriers they may experience in accessing the support services.

Another example comes from **Portugal**, where the Directorate-General of Health, with Rule 18/2020, warned that access to contraception and abortion are essential health services and proposed strategies for health professionals to optimize and maintain effective responses. The policy states that **hospital units must provide the necessary conditions for ensuring the presence of a companion during childbirth**. Mental health care, during pregnancy and postpartum, must be maintained and if necessary reinforced. Video consultations and teleconsultations are alternative forms of providing these types of care, under the terms of Rule 011/2020 of the DGS. Due to the increased risk of anxiety and mood disorders in the pandemic period, pregnant women should be asked about their emotional state at every contact.

Civil society: “the LGBTIQ+ Life in Lockdown survey” in Ireland

In various contexts where the policies lacked gender mainstreaming, civil society organisations intervened with initiatives aimed at mitigating the increasing inequalities.

For instance, to face the **lack of government statistics on the impact of COVID-19 policy responses on the LGBTIQ+ community in Ireland**, three national NGOs (LGBT Ireland, the National LGBT Federation (NXF) and the Gay Community News (GCN)) conducted the “[LGBTIQ+ Life in Lockdown Survey](#)”. This survey included a sample of **1,855 members of the LGBTIQ+ community**. The survey showed that 62% experienced a decline in their mental health during the lockdown, substantially higher than the impacts reported in the general population in recent surveys. **This survey took an intersectional approach, aiming to recruit a sample that was as representative of the LGBTIQ+ community as possible in terms of age, identity, geographic location, minority and socio-economic status**. One key finding is that LGBTIQ+ people who are additionally marginalised including LGBTIQ+ migrants, Traveller and Roma, refugees, older, living with a long-term disability, or other intersectional identities have been the most impacted amongst the LGBTIQ+ community.

The report on the survey issued three recommendations for future policies:

- 1) To recognise the additional challenges faced by members of the LGBTI+ community during this unprecedented crisis;
- 2) To ensure that LGBTI+ services are properly resourced and promoted, so that those who need them can be informed and have access. Funding models must be reassessed and restructured to help services deal with the crisis and the mental health issues that will arise as a result;
- 3) To allocate ringfenced funding for members of the LGBTI+ community who suffer intersectional discrimination, particularly in the health services sector.

➤ *RESISTIRÉ Recommendations: 10 Steps to mainstream gender in policies related to the pandemic*

- I. Early in the policy process, establish what are the main gender-related concerns in the policy area, what are the potential impacts of the pandemic on the policy area and how the pandemic may impact the policy area;
- II. Partner with CSOs and actors working on the ground with communities and vulnerable groups, investigate and issue reports and generate media coverage concerning the marginalised groups;
- III. Arrange cross-community, cross-sector, and cross-issue workshops/meetings to analyse policies impacts, particularly on the most vulnerable;
- IV. Use gender+ disaggregated data as much as possible; these are often generated by CSOs as can be seen in the LGBTQI+ survey above;
- V. Make sure that all objectives, targets, indicators are gender sensitive;
- VI. Establish mechanisms for gender sensitive monitoring and evaluation.
- VII. Distribute concrete responsibilities to dedicated actors (rather than taking the sole responsibility for all)
- VIII. Make sure that all actors involved have sufficient gender training.
- IX. Bring in external gender expertise and the involvement of target groups.
- X. Increase the participation of diverse women in policy making.

Ensuring gender-balanced decision-making and the involvement of civil society

Several studies highlight the extent of women's under-representation in decision-making and the invisibility of their voices in policy responses to the COVID-19 pandemic.

➤ *Background information*

During the pandemic, while many women have mainly been working behind the scenes – as nurses, medical doctors and so on – the public domain has been disproportionately occupied by men, responsible for the important decisions affecting citizens' everyday lives (EIGE, 2020).¹

A greater **representation of women**, together with a focus on **diversity and inclusion**, in decision-making, can make a significant contribution in overturning the worst effects of COVID-19 responses on inequalities. A higher women's presence in decision-making means that women's interests are more likely to be addressed in policy discussions and outcomes.

As a 2020 [report](#)² from McKinsey & Company states, "companies that lead on diversity have taken bold steps to strengthen inclusion. Early signs suggest that the COVID-19 crisis could deepen these trends." It also argues that "The penalty for lagging on gender diversity is growing, while top quartile companies are more likely to be at an advantage".

➤ *Policy mapping: main findings*

This lack of women in the response to the pandemic is one of the main findings from RESISTIRÉ. **In many countries the relevant decision-making positions were mainly held by men**, as most of the pandemic-related measures identified in the European countries³ were created at the level of the national government (with some exceptions observed in countries with a federal system), sometimes with the support of expert committees created ad-hoc to deal with the emergency.

Similarly, an analysis of the **gender composition of 115 expert and decision-making COVID-19 task forces** from 87 countries found that **85.2% of these groups were made up of mostly males, 11.4% predominantly contained females and only 3.5% of the groups had gender parity** (see Figure 1). The study found that men were also over-represented in global task forces to a similar extent as that of national ones. Thus, for example, the WHO's first, second and third International Health Regulations Emergency committees included 23.8%, 23.8% and 37.5% women, respectively (Van Daalen et al., 2020).

ANALYSIS OF GENDER COMPOSITION

Figure 1: Composition of 115 expert and decision-making COVID-19 task forces from 87 countries (based on Van Daalen et al. 2020 data)

Expert women’s voices have also been muted in the media. The Global Institute for Women’s Leadership at Kings College London analysed a sample of 146,867 articles published between March and July 2020. It found that just 5% of well-known STEM experts and 15% of well-known economists mentioned in these articles were women. Significant gender-gaps were also found in relation to references to politicians, as only 17% of those mentioned were women, meaning that for every mention of a female politician in an article about the COVID-19 crisis, there were five mentions of a male politician (Jones, 2020).

Figure 2: Percentage of well-known experts in different areas, divided by gender, mentioned in a sample of about 150 thousand articles published between March and July 2020 (based on Jones 2020 data)

In the UK, 43% of the government’s daily press briefings on the COVID-19 pandemic between March and May 2020 featured an all-male line up with no female politician or

expert present, with only one female cabinet member ever leading the briefing (Smith 2020).

Women’s organisations in civil society have also been excluded from decision-making around the responses to the pandemic. A rapid analysis of the gender makeup of COVID-19 response teams conducted by CARE in 30 countries (from both the global North and South) found that local women’s rights and women-led organisations and leaders were not included in decision-making around the response to the pandemic crisis, neither did they receive their share of funding. The report⁴ recommended that national governments should “work with diverse local women-led and women’s rights organisations, movements, and leaders to identify the barriers to women’s participation and leadership in decision-making structures and determine actions to address and dismantle those barriers”. It also recommended international NGOs to increase partnerships with women’s rights-and women-led organisations and to work with them to identify the barriers and possible solutions to their participation and leadership in decision-making structures.

➤ *Expert consultations: main findings*

IRELAND

In Ireland, the persistent lack of women in leadership roles and the low levels of women’s representation in Irish politics have been put in the spotlight during the COVID-19 crisis. The consensus among experts in Ireland was that having more women in decision-making roles could have identified, anticipated and ameliorated the gendered effects of COVID policies. In particular, they noted an absence of women’s representatives of vulnerable groups in policy discussions.

TURKEY

In Turkey, women’s groups and support networks were the most effective forms of help during the pandemic crisis in Turkey. The policies connected to the pandemic have created new opportunities for women from different social backgrounds to meet and discuss women’s situation, including the rise of GBV and the withdrawal of Turkey from the Istanbul Convention.

UNITED KINGDOM

consideration.

In Scotland, the Scottish Government has committed to developing a mainstreaming strategy and to improve data collection. Having visible female leaders pushing for gender equality, such as Nicola Sturgeon, has made a difference in bringing gender equality higher up on the agenda. However, what is particularly needed is greater gender competence within governmental delivery agencies and other decision-making bodies so that policies take women's lives into

CZECH REPUBLIC

The Czech Women's Lobby did draw attention to the fact that the Economic Recovery Committee was extremely male dominated, which led to policies that were not taking women into account.

In Czech Republic, people in power tend to be men. Therefore, COVID-19 policies, such as the lockdown, have not taken into account the realities of women's lives. Some of their consequences, such as increased care responsibilities, strongly impacted women. Women's organisations were mostly not very active on these issues because they themselves were impacted so strongly by the lockdown policies, that they had very little energy left to focus on these issues.

› *Better Stories*

Within RESISTIRÉ, we identify "Better Stories", a term taken from Dina Georgis (2013) for promising practices that identify how a given societal situation can be ameliorated to improve existing practices.

Women's representation in decision-making

In Lithuania, the effect of the government's gender composition appears to be relevant when considering policies directed at women. In April 2020, information emerged about the situation of expecting mothers, who were receiving a somewhat lower maternity and childcare allowance due to being furloughed and lost work income. One member of the Parliament (an opposition MP) registered an amendment to the Act on Social Insurance for Sickness and Maternity that would make it possible to exclude the furlough period from calculations of the maternity and childcare leave allowances. There was little public attention to the issue and the amendment was not approved by the Parliament, with some MPs stating that the loss to family income would be insignificant and no exceptions should be made that could burden the state budget. The measure was approved only after the election of 2020 and the change of the government [which became more gender-balanced].

When public institutions collaborate with civil society organisations

In Denmark, the Minister for the Social and the Elderly held monthly meetings with civil society organisations for long periods during the pandemic and [...] the chairwoman and co-chairwoman of the Council for Ethnic Minorities participated in several meetings with

the Minister of Foreign Affairs and Integration, the Minister of Health, and various other relevant authorities as well as NGOs.

In Sweden, a strong interaction was observed between public authorities, NGOs, and civil society. For instance, in relation to GBV the Association for municipalities and regions (SKR) began a review of the situation linked to COVID-19. Early contact was made with municipal sheltered housing in the metropolitan municipalities to get an idea of the situation and their preparedness. To better understand the situation on the ground, SKR initiated contact with SKR's women's peace network, the social manager network, and the network for development leaders for women's peace within the regional collaboration and support structures, RSS. Contact was also made with the police authority in Stockholm and the Finnish Shelter Services.

➤ *Recommendations*

Increase gender equality, diversity and inclusion in public authorities and decision-making bodies

1. Ensure gender parity in expert-decision making committees, task forces and advisory bodies.
2. Women should be represented at all levels of decision making. As our data show, having visible female leaders has a positive impact on gender equality. However, gender competence building, together with increased women's representation, should be implemented across government agencies and other decision making and implementing bodies.
3. Women and men from vulnerable groups should be represented in policy deliberations. Representation of women and men with a migration background, women and men from ethnic minority groups, as well as those representing people with different abilities, are among examples of such groups

Collaborate with Civil society organisations (CSOs)

The collaboration between public authorities and CSOs should be strengthened. Country examples show (e.g., in Sweden) the strategic importance of collaboration between central institutions and organisations at the regional and local level, particularly those that are in contact with vulnerable groups of women and men. The activities of CSOs targeting specific groups of people are for public authorities an excellent

example of the need to adopt intersectional approaches when addressing issues related to the pandemic.

Increase gender balance in media scientific and political communication

Scientific and political communication of the COVID-19 pandemic in the media cannot be the preserve of men alone, and women cannot be left with only minor and stereotypical roles in the communication process. More attention must also be given to different lines of communication in providing information to cover all segments of the population.

Gender equality plans should become mandatory for hospitals

The pandemic has made visible the need for hospitals to offer the adapted working conditions and to deliver a service of the highest quality. Healthcare workers are leaving the sector faster than ever because of poor working conditions, lack of an adequate work-life balance, and work-related safety and health risks, which were exacerbated during the pandemic. Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) are a proven method to initiate a process of sustainable institutional change to the benefit of the quality of care, that is linked to the motivation and well-being of the people working in hospitals.

› *Background Information*

The existing inequalities in the healthcare sector, and more specifically in hospitals, have been exacerbated due to the pandemic. **Decision-making mechanisms and management are male-dominated, while most healthcare workers, especially on the front line against the virus, are female.** To illustrate, in 2019, more than 70% of the global health workforce consisted of women, while men held about 75% of health leadership roles¹. More specifically, within the EU in the same year, 86% of personal care workers in health services were women, while women made up 89% nurses and midwives and 84% of associated professionals. In contrast, women made up only 52% of medical doctors².

Moreover, the psychosocial risks that healthcare workers - and especially women – have always had to face, have been exacerbated during the COVID-19 pandemic. **The prevalence of these risks is not just inherent to the tasks and workload, it is also due to the work's general organisation and management as well as the social context in which the job is carried out³, with (women) healthcare workers experiencing different kinds of harassment from patients, clients and co-workers, and also being subject to various patriarchal norms and assumptions regarding their work⁴.** Instances of harassment, bullying and violence against healthcare workers have increased worldwide during COVID-19⁵.

Structural gender inequalities result in the devaluation of care work, which is evident in the feminisation of the health sector. **Major improvements are needed in working conditions, at the level of recruitment, career progression, women in leadership**

positions, work-life balance, prevention of sexual harassment and violence, and psychosocial risks in general. The pressure to improve on all these dimensions has increased due to the pandemic, as these inequalities became more visible. Also, it has been hypothesised that handling the crisis may have been more efficient if the organisations adopted Gender Equality measures and diversity policies.

› *Institutional change through GEPs: similarities between the research and healthcare sectors*

An approach to promote the development of GEPs in hospitals can build on the experience gained in the higher education sector. One of the success factors in the research sector rests in the institutional change and the holistic approach: working on different domains of discrimination in parallel and making sure the measures proposed are integrated into the processes and effectively change the way the institution functions in a sustainable way.

Similarities exist between the two sectors in terms of hierarchy, paternalistic culture and power relations that lead to common inequality patterns. Implementing this recommendation could act as a living lab to improve the Occupational Safety and Health at work legislation on psycho-social risks at EU-level. Hospitals are an environment where these risks are probably higher than in many other sectors.

› *Better Stories*

Within RESISTIRÉ, we identify “Better Stories”, a term taken from Dina Georgis (2013) for promising practices that identify how a given societal situation can be ameliorated to improve existing practices.

Examples of GEPs in public hospitals are still very rare in the EU. Some countries, like France and Spain, have passed legislation that impose the development of a GEP or equivalent on public hospitals. The first examples of GEPs being implemented lack ambition and most often limit their actions to only a few domains, leading to a small impact and slow change.

Examples:

- [The GEP of GHU Paris](#)
- [The GEP of the Basque Health Agency](#)

➤ Recommendations

1. Make the development of a “Gender Equality Plan” (GEP) mandatory for all hospitals.

Impacts pursued with this recommendation:

1. Improved equality and diversity in the workplace
2. Encourage institutional change
3. Address and eliminate harassment issues
4. Raise standards for professional practices in the EU

2. Promote the development of holistic GEPs, addressing all the different domains where discriminations take place.

A holistic approach, that addresses in parallel different domains where discrimination takes place:

- **Work-life balance and organisational culture.** Work intensity, insufficient rest, a poor work-life balance, low wages, and numerous other causal factors within this female dominated sector lead to high psychosocial risks that need to be prevented through adequate collective measures. One such collective measure on the EU level could be to include a new ‘Daughter Directive’ within the Directive 89/391/EEC, on occupational health and safety, that recognises and protects against the psychosocial risks that are so prevalent in the healthcare sector.
- **Gender balance in leadership and decision-making.** Even if the sector is highly feminised, decision-making bodies are too often male dominated and embedded in a paternalistic culture.
- **Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.** Gender balance is important in all career paths inside hospitals.
- **Integration of the gender dimension into healthcare service delivery.** Discriminatory behaviours inside the organisation are connected with discrimination in medical treatment.
- **Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.** The hierarchic culture and the power relations create conditions for hidden gender-based harassment and violence.

3. Integrate the actions from the plan in hospital processes, leading to sustainable institutional change.

An institutional approach that embeds the changes into the bodies and processes of the organisation:

- **Public commitment:** a formal document signed by the top management, published on the institution’s website and widely disseminated within the institution and toward patients and other external stakeholders.
- **Dedicated resources:** committing resources and gender expertise to implement it. Earmarked funding should be available for staff positions such as Equality Officers or Gender Equality Teams.
- **Data collection and monitoring:** disaggregated sex/gender data across all staff categories, and annual reporting on gender imbalances based on the indicators; comprehensive evaluation approach. Disaggregated data collection must also be launched to monitor treatment delivery and efficiency among diverse groups of patients.
- **Capacity-building actions:** awareness-raising and training on gender equality and unconscious gender bias for staff and decision-makers; information and dissemination material, workshops or working groups dedicated to specific topics.

4. A process of development according to the following principles:

Intersectional/Gender+ Approach: While gender is at the centre of this recommendation, other integrated indicators should be taken into consideration to address other potential inequality grounds intersecting with gender, such as ethnicity, class, disability, age, religion/belief, sexual orientation and sexual identity, family composition and care duties, contractual status, language, citizenship).

Inclusiveness: The perspective of all stakeholders of the hospital (doctors, nurses, support and administrative staff, including temporary staff, subcontractors and trainees) and at different levels should be taken into account in identifying the measures to undertake. The patient perspective in its diversity and as the ultimate beneficiary should be included with the help of patient organisations.

Participatory Approach: Inclusiveness should be accomplished through participatory approaches and techniques that help to define meaningful measures to the actors involved, boosting their willingness to implement them, while respecting the organisational culture. Different and separate dynamic workshops can be envisaged with senior management and leadership posts, human resources and communication staff, medical staff, support staff, ... The techniques used have to be adapted to ensure they do not create an additional burden for overworked staff. For measures aimed at patients, patient and women's organisations should be included too.

Green for everyone. Promoting Green Spaces and Mitigating Gentrification

COVID-19 and the associated policy measures that curbed vast stretches of public life highlighted the need for more urban green spaces, as people started to utilise existing green areas significantly more (in countries where parks and other green spaces were not closed down). This trend also emphasised the fact that some neighbourhoods – often populated by vulnerable socioeconomic groups, such as ethnic minorities, low-skilled and informal workers, etc. – have a lot less green space than others, exacerbating physical and mental health problems, as well as making it more difficult for people to socialise and engage in community-building.

›Background Information

- Urban areas that have undergone greening often become gentrified: because green environments are in high demand on the housing market, property prices tend to rise in areas that implement greening measures, thereby pushing out people with low incomes and vulnerable groups. In fact, wealthy investors and companies increasingly develop costly and unaffordable infrastructures in less affluent neighbourhoods. This

leads to the intra-urban displacement of people with a low socioeconomic status, effectively preventing them from benefitting from any positive urban (re)development, like the expansion of green spaces.

- Levels of access to green areas, exposure to pollution, the effects of gentrification and the availability of recycling schemes analysed through a socioeconomic lens remain under-researched areas. There is currently too little data that is both representative and disaggregated by factors such as gender, socioeconomic status and education.
- There is a real opportunity now to improve this situation. Across various major European urban centres, a majority of respondents to public opinion polls carried out by YouGov between 14-21 May, 2020, expressed the need for better mobility policies and cleaner air in their cities, and demanded change in the outlook of urban life in the future¹.

➤ *Expert consultations and quantitative data: main findings*

According to the workshops and interviews with inequality experts that were organised by RESISTIRÉ, inequalities related to peoples' access to nature and green spaces have increased during the COVID-19 pandemic. People with a low socioeconomic status are often more dependent on public spaces like parks than those with access to private natural spaces (i.e., gardens). While some cities and countries kept green spaces open during their respective lockdowns, other areas/countries had a more restrictive approach and closed public green spaces. Even though these kinds of policies affected all citizens, the impacts were unequal across inequality grounds such as ethnicity and socioeconomic background. For those with no private gardens, the closure of public parks and gardens had a stronger negative impact on their physical and mental well-being.

Moreover, different neighbourhoods have differing amounts of green space within them, with poorer neighbourhoods often containing very little. This is further reinforced by the process of gentrification outlined previously. As a concrete example, certain lockdown policy measures in Spain temporarily increased environmental inequalities by only allowing residents to walk around in their general neighbourhood, which deprived people living in greyer neighbourhoods from enjoying nature.

The analysis of quantitative data in the RESISTIRÉ project² granted a few more insights: "A RAS (Rapid Assessment Survey) from Greece with 730 respondents aged over 18 years

old and living in urban areas indicates that women were more concerned about their neighbourhoods during the pandemic and moved around in them more. Among all respondents to this survey, concerns about urban space increased, especially as far as the quality of public space, walking conditions, and cycling facilities was concerned.”

➤ *Narratives: main findings*

Narratives collected by the RESISTIRÉ³ project have indicated some examples of how green spaces provided a vital component of people’s lives during the pandemic and how access to these spaces was sometimes denied. Below are two examples:

CROATIA

An elderly woman with a physical disability living in Zagreb, Croatia experienced the beginning of the pandemic in a locked-down residential home, where she was not able to see relatives or friends from outside. She was also unable to go outside to take care of her dog herself. Eventually, she decided to move to the house of her grandparents, which was located next to the coast in a more natural environment. Despite the scepticism of other people and the accessibility limitations she had to deal with, she experienced more joy. She loved to swim in the area, was able to spend more time with her dog, and even engaged with the local community to start a beehive on her own in a nearby abandoned village.

“My daily routine has become to ride every day by my wheelchair scooter six kilometres to that village, work with bees and prepare different healthy products for several hours, and then ride back. (...) I do not sell products, but ask people to donate money to the NGO I founded.”

SLOVENIA

Due to pandemic curbs a middle-aged mother from Ljubljana, Slovenia, was unable to leave her municipality and was, therefore, limited to very little green space during lockdown. She started to miss having a house with a garden (like her parents had) and did not find the green spaces within the city adequate for her needs. Municipal borders prevented her from accessing more expansive green areas, despite the fact that there are some nice parks just outside of the city.

“At that time, I really missed a house with a garden. I do not miss it otherwise, because I have great parks in short proximity of our apartment, but at the time of the lockdown and the limitations on movement I really missed it.”

› Better Stories

Within RESISTIRE, we identify “Better Stories”, a term taken from Dina Georgis (2013) for promising practices that identify how a given societal situation can be ameliorated to improve existing practices.

- A bottom-up initiative was started by local residents to develop and open a community-created urban garden in a formerly grey space in [Belfast](#). [Find out more](#).
- Pre-pandemic, the Finnish city of [Turku](#) started funding and organising 'safety walks' to engage its citizens in creating safer and more equal public spaces, including green spaces. This participatory approach tries to bring together a diverse group of residents of all genders, ages, and backgrounds. A similar approach targeted towards women in particular was used in [French cities](#) to promote gender mainstreaming. [Find out more](#).
- **London's Grow Back Greener Fund:** to stimulate a green urban recovery from COVID-19, the Greater London Authority awarded grants to community projects that applied for funding in [2021](#) (£700,000 for 34 approved projects) and it will fund additional community projects in [2022](#) that fall under the two broad themes of access to green space and climate adaptation & water. [Find out more](#).

› Recommendations

- Prioritise Green Space in Policymaking

Policymakers should make the accessibility of green spaces a priority when designing policies and engaging in urban planning. It is also important to lower green spaces' barriers to entry for users from vulnerable socio-economic groups (ethnic minorities, homeless people, people with disabilities, ...) with a particular attention to gender differences, for example by providing ample space and necessary services, and improving inclusivity and safety through adequate, inclusive and participatory design.

- **Green Public Spaces**

A more equitable distribution of green spaces should be encouraged by both policymakers and civil society organisations (CSOs) by repurposing (little-used) grey areas and greening them, especially in disadvantaged neighbourhoods. This can be done on both a small scale with relatively little resources, for example by planting small groups of trees and/or flower boxes, or starting a community garden in a street or back alley, as well as on a larger scale by creating and expanding parks and urban forests. It is imperative to take a strongly participative approach when creating or altering green spaces and to enable the local community to engage in co-creation processes to shape their surroundings. Green spaces will, in this case, not only lead to improved physical and mental health outcomes, but also to increased social cohesion and community development.

- **Adopt a Holistic Policy Approach**

Any initiative to green a neighbourhood should include policy measures to prevent an increase in housing prices and general cost of living. To adequately mitigate gentrification, a holistic approach is needed to ensure that actions from different policy domains can be combined effectively and that new policies can be integrated when necessary. To illustrate, this would mean that efforts to green a neighbourhood have to be combined with a host of social policies that can improve income levels and employment rates. Also important is the simultaneous development of affordable housing and accompanying social infrastructure (i.e., local services) in the area to prevent a strong upward trend in house prices. This could be combined with rent control and rent freezing policies to be as effective as possible. The effort to promote green spaces can, itself, be utilised as an instrument in socioeconomic policy, as they can foster social cohesion and play an important role in people's general wellbeing.

- **Role of Local Governments**

Cities and municipalities, due to their status as landowners, have a crucial role to play and should prioritise community development rather than economic gains. Measures such as promoting good-quality high-capacity buildings instead of single-family houses, or keeping housing prices affordable and in line with the median income of residents, are crucial to avoid gentrification. Combined with measures that boost local economic activity, such as local currencies and the creation and protection of (green) commons, these policies will lead to increased living standards and well-being, while protecting vulnerable populations.

- **User Involvement and Community Mobilisation**

Another way of mitigating gentrification is to have users (i.e., the original residents of a neighbourhood) participate in the creation and definition of new green spaces. This would ensure that they are included in a feedback loop with (local) policymakers and civil servants, and that they actively shape – in terms of practical, environmental, and aesthetic aspects – the local green spaces in which they live. The same can be true for the ‘programming’ of green spaces: locals should influence the programming of activities and events within a green space so that it becomes more attractive to them and less relevant for newer groups who might be economically disruptive. In these ways, green spaces can be slowly leveraged as social spaces for local mobilisation against gentrification and for promoting a genuine community feeling.

To enable developments like this, positive evidence-based narratives around green interventions and co-creation should be constructed and propagated by local policymakers and CSOs through multimedia channels, community organisations (like housing cooperatives, local churches and schools), and local businesses, so that potential users become more aware of green spaces’ benefits and become more involved in participative processes that relate to them. Special attention should be paid by these policymakers and CSOs to utilise a gender+ approach and include marginalised groups, for example by facilitating bottom-up initiatives and making inclusive co-creation toolkits widely available. Another method of doing this is to label green spaces in a gender+ way by naming them after inspirational (historical) members of disadvantaged communities. Inclusivity can also be promoted by not just emphasising the diverse identities of people that (might) use green spaces, but also by accepting and enabling all kinds of practical behaviours in and specific uses of green spaces.

Care and Crisis: Fostering a Paradigm Shift

The COVID-19 crisis has reinforced many pre-existing inequalities, and simultaneously made them more visible. The lockdowns brought with them the closure of many care facilities and the requirement to stay at home, which strongly impacted people with caring responsibilities, whether it be for children, elderly people, people with a disability, and/or others. But the situation impacted men and women in different ways, as the gender care gap was exacerbated and women took up more care work. The gender pay gap likely contributed to this trend: because women tend to earn lower wages and work in part-time jobs more often, they were the most likely to have to give up their paid work within a couple in order to sustain the increased caring duties of a household.

› *Background information*

With the onset of the pandemic, an additional dimension of the gendered division of labour suddenly came into focus. The rapid and widespread adoption of telework caused a significant increase in the prevalence of remote working, which, in turn, allowed for (but not necessarily resulted in) changes in the household distribution of care and domestic labour. The findings in this regard are ambiguous: while some fathers have taken up more care work since they started working from home, the existing gender care gap in Europe meant that the immediate increased

burden of care due to the movement restrictions almost exclusively fell on women.

› *Quantitative data: main findings*

The analysis of quantitative data in the RESISTIRÉ project¹ revealed that: "The greater time spent on caring for dependent children and older adults by women during the pandemic (gender care gap) and a lack of associated support appear to have had negative consequences for women's performance at work, time for recreation, work-life balance, income, and possibilities of accepting a job. There have also been consequences for

women's wellbeing. Studies find that the pandemic had a greater impact on women's mental health than men's and that, compared to men, women felt more overwhelmed, exhausted and stressed and less satisfied with work, family life and life in general. Several studies suggest that women's poorer mental health outcomes are directly linked to the gender care gap and mothers in particular were found to suffer."

While men and non-primary caretakers have been made more aware of the importance of sharing caring tasks and some of them have actually taken up more care work in the household, this change is likely to revert back to the status quo if it is not maintained with a shift in policies which incentivise shared caring duties and foster cultural change.

For instance: "Many RAS (Rapid Assessment Surveys) show that fathers increased their contribution to childcare during the pandemic as a result of working from home, which led to greater flexibility in work hours and reduced commute times. (...) A longitudinal panel study organised by three Dutch universities with households in the Netherlands found that the proportion of fathers reporting greater involvement in childcare increased between April (22%) and June 2020 (31%), however by September of the same year it had decreased to 23% and in November it reduced further still (18%)"².

To conclude, it was women who bore the brunt of the increase in unpaid care work and the decrease in employment, leading to a widening of the gender pay gap, labour gap and care gap. There has been insufficient support for reconciling the demands of care, domestic labour, and work in the light of school closures and the increase in teleworking.

› Narratives: main findings

Narratives collected by the RESISTIRÉ project have indicated some examples of how domestic work, and especially care work, has increasingly fallen on the shoulders of women. Below are two examples:

Caring for a disabled child

ITALY

An Italian woman close to retirement age has both a professional career and caring responsibilities for her son, who has a serious disability. It was possible to manage this before COVID-19 because of a set of routines, but this ended once the pandemic started. During the lockdown, the care facility her son attended closed, which meant that she had to work from home while also caring for him. Her husband is old-fashioned and believes it is not his duty to take care of the caring tasks around their son and their household.

This was close to impossible for her, and life at that moment was very difficult.

“With the onset of COVID-19, my life suddenly exploded. The management of my son fell solely on me. During those months, I faced all the same difficulties that other women may have faced, but mine were aggravated by the fact that I could not escape, not even to take refuge in my work, which had become nearly impossible to perform. My smart working experience was consistently burdened by the presence of my son, who constantly demanded attention. Before I was a caregiver only on Saturday, Sunday, and during the holidays. Now I am a caregiver every day.”

Teleworking with a small child

GREECE

A working middle-aged mother living in Greece had to devote more of her time to taking care of her small child when the pandemic started, as education moved online and her son had only just started the first grade. To be able to do this, she had to combine these caretaking responsibilities with her (newly imposed) telework arrangement. Her ex-partner, meanwhile, refused to share this burden with her, even when she had other important appointments.

“I felt that I had to become a housewife, drinking coffee with other mothers, and playing with the kids in the morning and then trying to work. At work I could not cope. His father did not help us at all.”

› Better Stories

Within RESISTIRE, we identify “Better Stories”, a term taken from Dina Georgis (2013) for promising practices that identify how a given societal situation can be ameliorated to improve existing practices.

SPAIN

In Spain, policies tried to keep a balance between work and family responsibilities (primarily care) by **allowing a reduction of working hours for employees** who had to take care of family members due to COVID-19 reasons. Some regional governments provided economic compensation for the loss of income.

Also in Spain, workers (including the self-employed) benefitting from a special allowance for the care of a minor with a severe illness (cancer, etc.) kept receiving that allowance even if their contract was suspended or their working hours were reduced due to the COVID-19 crisis. Moreover, the allowance was declared compatible with unemployment and other schemes for self-employed workers who had to stop their activities.

NETHERLANDS

In the Netherlands, several organisations and businesses came up with their own ideas to relieve the increased care burden on their employees. Internet and data provider VodafoneZiggo proclaimed that children were a priority during the pandemic in order to lower stress on employees with children. For instance, these employees received a maximum of seven extra vacation days to care for their children. SURF,

a cooperation of different schools, universities and research institutions, allowed its employees to register 'corona hours' in its work hours system, meaning hours when they had to take care of their children. These hours did not have to be compensated for later on. Law firm NautaDutilh ensured that employees with children could be reimbursed for a babysitter at home and Tilburg University provided employees with full pay even if they were not able to work full hours during the day due to care responsibilities.

UNITED KINGDOM

In the UK, the Dope Black Dads podcast platform provides a safe space for mutual learning and exchange among black fathers. They are able to share various experiences on the intersection of fatherhood and race, including on the risk of discrimination for both them and their children/families.

➤ Recommendations

- Recognise the Complex and Multifaceted Nature of Work

From a policy perspective, 'work' should be viewed not only as formally compensated labour, but also as unpaid work (care and domestic work) and informal work arrangements. Thus, it is crucial to take into account how work and labour market policies impact those in unpaid and informal work arrangements, because people in these arrangements are affected by them, but are often also most vulnerable. Furthermore, there should be

policies specifically addressing the needs of people in unpaid and informal work arrangements. Additionally, recognising work in this manner could facilitate a cultural shift in how people generally think about work and, especially, where work takes place (in the home, as well as in the workplace).

EVOLUTION OF 'WORK'

- Promote 'Caring Workplaces' among Employers

A caring workplace is one that recognises the importance of employees' work-life balance and inclusive workspaces, as well as the fact that care work is demanding and, as such, should be equally divided within households. Caring workplaces' practices and policies should focus on the recognition of care as part of the working hours of an employee, and promote healthy balance between work and private life. The measures listed below can provide both employees and employers with multiple benefits, including an increase in the well-being of workers, a reduction of psycho-social risks at the workplace, a reduction in absenteeism and sick leaves, increased levels of creativity and greater sense of belonging and solidarity among employees.

- Caring workplace policies should concretely recognise that care work still happens after the paid working hours of an employee, and therefore should promote a healthy division between labour at work and at home. This can be done by providing more flexibility to working hours and more control to employees in order to organise their duties.
- Caring workplace policies should explicitly state that most caring roles are unequal within households, and that care is a responsibility disproportionately covered by women in society. Therefore, mindful of this necessary division of care roles within households, they should incentivise support for care hours and leaves for male

employees, and ensure that these hours are used by all workers, regardless of rank within a workplace. This equal treatment and responsibilities should be highlighted, and is key to ensuring and communicating that taking time off from work to care for others does not have a negative connotation within workplaces.

- Caring workplace policies could focus on helping those with care responsibilities in delegating care. Offering employees details about local spaces of care/caring institutions (day-care, retirement homes, hospices, and hospitals) as well as incentivising their use by giving employees structural (or monetary) support in utilising these care spaces can directly encourage those with caring duties to use these services. Even more concretely, employers can create a mainstreamed flow between workplaces and caring facilities, as well as a more institutionalised recognition of the caring duties of workers, by establishing formal relationships and partnerships with these kinds of institutions.

- Expand Care Facilities

Governments should provide free and accessible care facilities. These should be nearby in order to reduce the travel burden, which mainly falls on women. Attention should be paid to those in irregular conditions, such as night workers, who should have access to special 24-hour childcare facilities. Particular attention should also go to childcare facilities for children under three years old, as the [Barcelona Objectives](#) on the development of childcare facilities have not yet been reached in a number of countries and can be made more ambitious. The facilities for children younger than three years are sparser, stemming from the expectation that it is the responsibility of the mother to take care of the child in these years.

- Care Leave Policy

Care leave policies should explicitly remind employers and employees that care should be an equal duty within households, and that this care often disproportionately falls on the shoulders of women, whether they are in a relationship or not. Moreover, rather than developing care leave policies in isolation, they should be integrated in more flexible work schedules, which can accommodate the various needs of workers. Care leave can have the detrimental effect of furthering the care gap if implemented in isolation, as it can create an incentive for non-primary caretakers to let their partners take up the care burden. Therefore, it should be strongly encouraged to reshape working schedules while taking into account the heterogeneous needs and duties of workers alongside the proposition of care leave policies.

- Paternity Leave Policy

Paternity leave should be as long as maternity leave, and remunerated, compulsory and untransferable. This would not only give options to fathers on paper, but also in practice, whereas now fathers often cannot take up their full paternity leave. This policy would directly challenge cultural assumptions and customs about women being the primary responsible ones for children.

- Make Men's Care More Visible

Showcasing examples of changes in the values, actions and decisions of men by, for example, highlighting men with a political background involved in gender equality or reversing stereotypical depictions of caring roles. This would help create healthy role models for young men and lead to more equal and open caring roles and gender roles. An initiative like this can be carried out by both policymakers and employers through promotional campaigns.

- Approach Care from an Intersectional Perspective

There is a need for an intersectional approach when designing care policies, with a focus on vulnerable groups in relation to care. Some types of workers are disproportionately burdened by unequal care arrangements (i.e., night workers, minimum wage workers, ...), while some social groups (ethnic minorities, same-sex couples, single parents, sex workers, ...) might also face discrimination, stigmatisation, and racism when trying to make use of

care facilities and policies. Any policy or campaign should make sure to adequately address these different situations and guarantee equal rights and treatment for all.

Reinforcing EU-level action to combat Gender-based violence through the Istanbul Convention

Emerging global and national data show increases in gender-based violence and increases in the reported number of cases of gender-based violence against women and LGBTQI persons during the COVID-19 pandemic. The failure to finalise the adoption of the Istanbul Convention at the EU level is a contributing factor to increasing the conditions for and occurrences of gender-based violence during the pandemic.

› *Background information*

The Istanbul Convention (Council of Europe, 2011) is the first legally-binding instrument at the European level for preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence. Yet, it has not yet been ratified by all EU member countries, and after 10 years, the EU accession process is still not finalized. In many countries that have signed and ratified the Convention (see Figure 1), its implementation has been slow and ineffective, in some cases resulting in significant backlash (resulting in withdrawal in the case of Turkey in 2021 and preparations for withdrawal in Poland).

**THE COUNCIL OF EUROPE'S
ISTANBUL CONVENTION ON
VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN**

- RATIFIED / IN FORCE**
- SIGNED, NOT RATIFIED**
- NOT SIGNED**
- WITHDRAWN**

Figure 1: The situation of the Istanbul Convention in Europe. The EU as a whole signed the convention on 13/06/2017, but has not yet ratified it; source = [Council of Europe](#) (last updated 24/09/2021).

Emerging global and national data, including the results from RESISTIRÉ¹, show **increases in gender-based violence** and increases in the reported number of cases of gender-based violence against **women and LGBTQI persons**. The accompanying economic crisis and increasing unemployment (experienced in many countries) have also had an **adverse effect on domestic violence and its prevention**, where economic hardship and unemployment have intensified, creating further inequalities and increasing the risk of violence. With the additional challenges of pandemic lockdown and limited mobility, the economic crisis has also made women more reluctant to leave their partners or impose restriction orders against them. Hunger and the survival of the family have become priority issues, displacing efforts to address domestic violence. These examples point to the significance of adopting an intersectional approach to gender-based violence, exploring the context-specific intersections of gender, sexuality, class, ethnicity, nationality, and citizenship-status.

The COVID-19 pandemic is not the underlying cause of gender-based violence, but it has provided a window of opportunity and generated a momentum to mobilize against the imbalance of power, resources and control that are at the heart of GBV. This imbalance, in turn, stems from inequalities based on gender and sexuality, discriminatory attitudes and beliefs, gender stereotypes, social norms that tolerate and perpetuate violence and abuse, and not least, from societal structures that replicate inequality and discrimination.

➤ *Policy mapping: main findings*

The reports produced by the RESISTIRÉ's National Researchers underline how for many countries there are still major difficulties in the adoption or implementation of the Istanbul

Convention. Some examples below:

CROATIA

The provisions of the Istanbul Convention also demand investments and significant budget, otherwise it remains, as they say in Croatia, “a dead letter on paper”. Three years since the ratification of the Istanbul Convention, no significant budget allocations have been seen.

HUNGARY

In the field of violence against women “a counter-measure” has been introduced during the COVID-19 restrictions: the Parliament adopted on 5 May 2020 a political declaration (Vejkey et al., 2020) against the ratification of the Istanbul Convention, both by Hungary, and by the European Union. The Hungarian parliament has rejected the ratification of a treaty to combat violence against women, backing a government declaration that the measure promotes “destructive gender ideologies” and “illegal migration”.

TURKEY

On March 20, 2021, without any discussion, Turkey withdrew from the Istanbul Convention by the decision of the President. Their main argument was that LGBTI+’s have become more visible by taking power from the Istanbul Convention. In the same way, they argued that this convention was contrary to the ‘family culture’ and they argued that the Istanbul Convention should be abolished for the protection of the family.

POLAND

In 2015, Poland ratified the Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence (the so-called Istanbul Convention) but it is permanently contested by ruling party and conservative circles. The Convention has never been fully implemented into the Polish law.

➤ *Narratives: main findings*

Narratives collected by the RESISTIRÉ project² showed several ways in which the pandemic had a strong influence on issues related to gender-based violence. Below an example from Turkey:

*“After Turkey's withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention, I have been attacked on the streets several times. Even I could not count it. I used to go out with my make-up and clothes on the nights that I was performing, I was exposed to a glance and a skirmish at most. It was like this for years. But now, people's eyes have become demonic. Their way of behaving, talking ...Taxis! Most people were also experiencing physical attacks before the pandemic. I guess I was lucky in that regard. I did not encounter much harassment and violence before the pandemic. But right now, I'm really worried about my life. When I go out to work, I am afraid to dress, I remove my make-up and change on the way home. Because I've seen what can happen in that case. I don't go out without a *madi şugariyet* (Lubunca – tools that are carried for self-defence) with me. For example, I have a small whip. At least, it scares people a little.”*

“Before the pandemic, I never worried about my life when I was working outside. These attacks occur at night when it is not too late, and people are still on the street. As per the ban (in the scope of pandemic measures), music must be shut at 12:00 / midnight.”

› Better Stories

Within RESISTIRE, we identify “Better Stories”, a term taken from Dina Georgis (2013) for promising practices that identify how a given societal situation can be ameliorated to improve existing practices.

- A new package of measures against violence was adopted by the City of Vienna in June 2021. Already being implemented is the construction of a 5th women's shelter, which is to be built by 2022. In addition, a women's shelter is being converted into a women's shelter with a focus on girls and young women. Vienna thus meets the requirements of the Istanbul Convention and even exceeds them with the construction of the 5th women's shelter. This will increase the available shelter places to 225.
- Domestic violence is considered to be the main form of violence in Luxembourg. Other forms, such as physical, sexual, FGM or forced marriage have been more recently addressed (due to implementation of the Istanbul Convention). The focus is still on domestic violence.

› Recommendations

1. Strengthen the EU legal framework
 - It is crucial that the EC finalises the accession of the EU to the Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic

violence, known as the Istanbul Convention (see Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025).

- EU institutions should encourage ratification to the Convention, for instance, by making it a requirement to receive funds.
- Given the prevalence and grave consequences of gender-based violence, there is a dire need for the EU to adopt its own legal framework on combating this phenomenon, establishing binding minimum standards for all EU Member States, through the adoption of a horizontal directive to address new challenges posed by the pandemic (e.g. how to respond in lockdown conditions) and the socio-economic changes that it has resulted in (e.g. redressing the effects the pandemic had on vulnerable groups such as victims of GBV).
- All EU-level legal and administrative actions regarding gender-based violence should pay utmost attention to intersectionality and inclusion from a gender+ perspective.
- Make sure that the views and recommendations proposed by CSOs (in particular, organisations working with victims and survivors of gender-based violence) are effectively taken into account when developing EU-level policies on GBV.
- The EU should develop directives and regulations specifically pointing out the judicial cooperation in criminal matters under the legal framework of GBV (especially as regard to crime prevention and the rights of victims of crime), instead of under gender equality and asylum policy.

2. Collect data and good practices

- Funding and other resources should be allocated to ensure data collection and monitoring at the national and the EU level for GBV in cooperation with CSOs, universities and social workers
- Measures such as home confinement have created a particular set of challenges to the provision of services for victims/survivors of gender-based violence and reinforced the need to develop flexible and resilient systems of response and support. The EU should create a transnational platform for the exchange of challenges and inspiring practices to ensure access for all victims and survivors of violence to essential services.

3. Foster prevention programs and awareness campaigns

- Education and training are key actions to prevent GBV. The Gender Equality Strategy addresses these points, and must be urgently put into action.
- There is a dire need for concerted EU-level actions for developing, funding and encouraging awareness raising campaigns and prevention mechanisms that target (potential) perpetrators of gender-based violence.

4. Make sure nobody is left behind (intersectionality)

- To ensure the accessibility of protection and support mechanism for all victims and survivors of gender-based violence, it is crucial to adopt a gender+ intersectional approach (addressing among other categories of vulnerability, age, sexual orientation, gender identity, ethnicity, race, citizenship status, language, literacy, education level, digital literacy, dis-abilities, employment status, urban-rural divide, homelessness, etc.) in developing protection and support programs that incorporate all needs (from shelters to legal and psychological) support.

Illustration: Aslı Alpar

Improving national responses to gender-based violence: lessons from the pandemic crisis

THE SHADOW PANDEMIC

Emerging global and national data show increases in gender-based violence and increases in the reported number of cases of gender-based violence against women and LGBTQI persons during the COVID-19 pandemic. RESISTIRÉ analysis shows that

a majority of countries failed to address issues of gender-based violence in their COVID-19 policy response and while civil society organisations managed to react in some instances, the pandemic also put pressure and circumscribed their range of activities.

› *Background information*

Gender-based violence against women is a widespread, global problem connected to health, crime, capital, economy, and inequality, and with pandemic proportions: **one in three women worldwide have been subjected to physical or sexual violence** by a current or former intimate partner. Similarly, **LGBTIQ+ youth and adults face widespread gender-based and phobic violence at home and outside**. This shadow pandemic has been exacerbated by the very measures (such as lockdowns, stay-at-home measures, and online schooling) put in place to mitigate the “other” pandemic, COVID-19.

Emerging global and national data, including the results from RESISTIRÉ¹, show increased incidence of gender-based violence including violence against LGBTQI persons specifically. The accompanying economic crisis and increasing unemployment (experienced in many countries) have also had an adverse effect on domestic violence and its prevention, where **economic hardship and unemployment have intensified, creating further inequalities and increasing the risk of violence**. With the additional challenges of pandemic lockdown and limited mobility, the economic crisis has also made women more reluctant to leave their partners or impose restriction orders against them. Hunger and survival of the family have become priority issues, displacing efforts to address domestic violence. These examples point to the **significance of adopting an intersectional approach to gender-based violence**, exploring the context-specific intersections of gender, sexuality, class, ethnicity, nationality, and citizenship-status.

› *Analysis of quantitative data: main findings*

Studies on help-seeking show **increases in calls to hotlines and contacts with shelters**. They also show that victims/survivors **seek psychological care from their GPs rather than from the criminal justice system and the police**, meaning they may receive less support and access to resources. While help-seeking through **contacts with shelters have increased** (Figure 1), there are opposite cases: Some feminist organisations have pointed to the **difficulty women have been facing in lockdown conditions contacting support services** without the knowledge of the violent partner (e.g., Turkey).

CHANGES IN LEVEL OF DEMAND FOR SERVICES DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

How would you describe the level of demand for your services during Covid-19 compared with before the pandemic?

Figure 1: Changes in level of demand for services during the pandemic. Source: online survey conducted by EIGE2 with representatives of providers of services for victims of GBV in Europe (35 respondents from 17 member states).

Studies also show that domestic violence against young women and LGBTIQ+ who returned to their family homes during the pandemic have increased. This captures a form of re-traditionalisation of gender roles and violence as control and surveillance. Yet, pointing out the pandemic rather than male violence as the cause for increased GBV during this period is problematic in creating solutions. The importance and necessity of finding new ways for data collection (including the use of individual testimonies to understand the emerging challenges), developing new monitoring mechanisms, and designing new forms of support and solidarity services (based on existing models) have become evident.

Studies that explored the availability and provision of services for those experiencing gender-based violence demonstrated that due to the increased need for assistance, pressure was placed upon shelters and charitable organisations that far exceeded their capability – except for in countries where extra funding and additional support were given from either the state (Sweden) or private sources (France). These latter ‘anomalies’ or deviations provide better stories, and a basis for recommendation. COVID-19 restrictions have led to a lack of access to services; reduced availability of shelters for their protection; and difficulties in retaining and supporting staff. The reliance of most services – although not all – on external funding significantly undermined the resilience of these organisations to sudden crisis, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. These organisations are likely to continue to suffer post-pandemic, as they will be left without reserve funds.

In summary, *during the pandemic women and LGBTIQ+ experiencing domestic violence have relied more on 1) online services, rather than audio hotlines, 2)*

healthcare providers, NGOs, and local pharmacies, rather than the police.

SUPPORT AND SOLIDARITY SERVICES

› Narratives: main findings

Narratives collected by the RESISTIRÉ project² showed several ways in which the pandemic had a strong influence on issues related to GBV. Below an example from Italy that underlines the increased request for shelters:

“I can also tell you about domestic violence. It increased enormously during the pandemic. Even where it didn't exist before, it has unfortunately occurred, in some situations. As the owner of a shelter for adoptive children, I received so many calls from social workers and other agencies, seeking my help. They asked me if I could take in women who had been victims of abuse. But I only take in minors, so it would have been too difficult for me to deal with more problems on my own. Anyway, it ended up costing me so much to say no.”

In addition, experts and professionals consulted within the RESISTIRÉ activities underlined that:

- Lockdown and confinement measures increased inequalities related to gender-based violence and made the tools to combat GVB more difficult to access.
- The notion of home as a place of safety, which forms the basis for policy on isolation and/or confinement in the home, was problematized since it neglects and worsens the situation of victims/survivors of multiple forms of gender-based violence in the home.
- Women by far have been the most disproportionately affected group in the context of gender-based violence, in particular, women living with perpetrators; women in trafficking or prostitution; and undocumented migrant women.
- Even in countries where services related to gender-based violence were declared essential there were still obstacles for women to get the information and access these services.
- Women with low digital literacy were reported to be vulnerable since they could not make use of digital solutions for contacting services without being overheard or leaving traces. Such tools exclude those who do not access to devices and

networks, and those who do not have the skills to use existing devices or networks.

› Better Stories

Within RESISTIRE, we identify “Better Stories”, a term taken from Dina Georgis (2013) for promising practices that identify how a given societal situation can be ameliorated to improve existing practices.

Policies

GBV and Technologies

TURKEY

The Women Emergency Support Application (KADES) is a mobile app launched in 2018 in Turkey for women who have been subjected to violence to report and call for support. It is a joint project prepared by the Ministry of Interior and the General Directorate of Security. Women who download this app register with ID numbers, and when they make a report of violence, this notification is forwarded to the nearest police station. If the person allows, location detection is also performed through this application. Instead of calling the police directly by phone during the pandemic, it was thought that easier support would be requested via the mobile app. KADES mobile app started to serve in a total of 6 languages, including Turkish, as of 07.03.2021.

GBV and Publics spaces

SPAIN

In Spain, the regional governments adhered to Mascarilla-19 initiative. It was an additional tool for women that suffer gender-based violence to raise the alarm in a safe way. During lockdown, women could go to any pharmacy and ask for a “Mask-19”. This word would alert the pharmacy staff, who would call the emergency number 112 and raise the alarm. During the lockdown, all shops in Spain were closed, except supermarkets and pharmacies. To go to these facilities was one of the few exceptions where people were allowed to leave their homes. This, in addition to the fact that the perpetrator was at home almost all the time, provided a space for women to report that they were suffering violence at home. This initiative spread to several other countries.

Civil society

In contexts where the policies to contrast the increase in GBV were weak or absent, civil society intervened with initiatives aimed at mitigating the increasing inequalities.

GBV and intersectionality

GREECE

In Greece, an initiative organised by the NGO DIOTIMA with the support of the International Rescue Committee, was launched to respond to the needs of the populations that were stranded on the island of Lesbos because of the geographic restrictions imposed during the pandemic. These migrants, asylum seekers and refugees were forced to isolate in the crowded camp of Kara Tepe, which was created after the old one of Moria was burnt down. Isolation and overcrowding have made these populations more vulnerable to GBV and the initiative was aimed at providing support, information and protection to victims and potential victims. In the emergency conditions of COVID-19, the program offered psychosocial support, legal support and temporary shelter for survivors of GBV.

Information pack for Traveller and Roma women

IRELAND

In Ireland, the legal system is of little use to people who are highly disempowered, such as Traveller and Roma women. These are women who have often reading difficulties and/or very little education. They also belong to a community who don't trust or who fear the police (Gardai). Furthermore, Traveller and Roma women do not trust the state system, so they fear that if they call the police, their children could be taken into care by the state.

Pavee Point Traveller and Roma Centre, in collaboration with other Travellers' rights groups throughout Ireland developed an information pack that includes a barring and safety order leaflet, with or without audio, and a barring and safety order animation. It has been developed by Traveller women for Traveller women and the audio animation provides very clear information in the language that they use, so that it is easy for them to understand. The aim of this initiative was to close the inequalities gap between women Travellers and the settled community in access to rights. While directed mainly at Traveller and Roma women, it also takes an intersectional approach.

Training for operators

ITALY

'Not Alone' is an integrated programme that was implemented by Save the Children in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. It aims to provide support (material, psychological, social, educational, etc.) to children and young people living in vulnerable families and in situations of hardship (including, therefore, for example, unaccompanied foreign minors). The programme provides (among other things) guidelines for operators in the field so that they can detect dangerous situations for women and children (e.g., domestic violence) as soon as

possible and facilitate their escape.

Technology and accessibility

TURKEY

The KADES app, developed in Turkey and described above, proved to be an interesting tool to support victims of GBV. At the same time, the lack of mobile devices was a barrier to accessing this tool. For this reason, the “Turkish Federation of Women’s Associations (TKDF)” and “Sabancı Foundation”, in collaboration with a technology retail company, launched the joint project “Technology for Women, Solidarity for all of us”. The goal of the project was to collect second-hand smartphone, fix and deliver them to women in need.

GBV and the importance of data

IRELAND

To face the lack of government statistics on the impact of COVID-19 policy responses on the LGBTQ+ community in Ireland, three national NGOs (LGBT Ireland, the National LGBT Federation (NXF) and the Gay Community News (GCN)) conducted the “LGBTI+ Life in Lockdown Survey”³. This survey included a sample of 1,855 members of the LGBTQ+ community. The survey showed that 62% experienced a decline in their mental health during the lockdown, substantially higher than the impacts reported in the general population in recent surveys. This survey took an intersectional approach, aiming to recruit a sample that was as representative of the LGBTQ+ community as possible in terms of age, identity, geographic location, minority and socio-economic status. One key finding is that LGBTQ+ people who are additionally marginalised including LGBTQ+ migrants, Traveller and Roma, refugees, older, living with a long-term disability, or other intersectional identities have been the most impacted amongst the LGBTQ+ community. The report on the survey issued three recommendations for future policy:

- 1) To recognise the additional challenges faced by members of the LGBTI+ community during this unprecedented crisis;
- 2) To ensure that LGBTI+ services are properly resourced and promoted, so that those who need them can be informed and have access. Funding models must be reassessed and restructured to help services deal with the crisis and the mental health issues that will arise as a result;
- 3) To allocate ringfenced funding for members of the LGBTI+ community who suffer intersectional discrimination, particularly in the health services sector.

➤ *Recommendations*

1. Develop multi-sectoral collaboration and intersectional coalitions
(For national authorities and local authorities)

The homeless, prisoners, ethnic minorities, people living in camps or substandard housing, have seen their living conditions dramatically worsened and are at risk of increased forms of violence.

- Apply an intersectional approach to all policies related to GBV.
- Promote the collaboration (by national and local authorities) with feminist, and LGBTIQ+, and other groups' organisations in designing solutions that address both the pandemic-specific challenges, as well as long-term eradication of violence.

2. End the data gap to make informed decisions

(For national and local authorities, with collaboration by CSOs)

There is a lack of adequate and comparable data related to GBV. On the one hand, collection of data usually focuses on number of murders and number of reports to police, and in the latter case, underreporting is an issue. More comprehensive data is required.

- Collect, monitor and analyse data on GBV to understand the causes and nature of GBV and to have informed evidence.
- Conduct surveys to reach potential victims beyond the official statistics on reports and femicides, and involve different stakeholders (e.g., CSOs) in the process.

3. Strengthen support services in times of emergency, Ensure resilience

(For national authorities and local authorities)

Results from RESISTIRÉ showed that one key challenge that emerged during the pandemic was the difficulty in reconciling continuity and quality of services. In particular, changing regulations, increasing demands for help and lack of resources (human and financial) hampered the access to support services. To ensure resilience of these services in the event of future crisis:

- Support services for victims of GBV should be declared essential, ensuring accessibility to all and safe conditions of access;
- Additional funding should be allocated to respond to crisis situations and make sure all services (shelter, counselling etc.) keep running.

4. GBV and ICTs

(For national and local authorities, CSOs)

One of the consequences of the pandemic has been the increased use of technology (telephone, video calls, chats, etc.) to provide long-distance support to victims of violence. However, as highlighted above by the Turkish experience with KADES, these technologies are not accessible to everyone, and care has to be taken to ensure that the conversations and data provided are safe and anonymous. Moreover, there has been an increase in violence perpetrated in digital spaces (cyberviolence).

- Continue promoting the use of ICT as an additional tool in GBV prevention and women support. The use of ICT provides a tool to reach women in rural areas, who are otherwise difficult to reach.

- Ensure accessibility, safety and anonymity when using digital technologies. In this sense, provide training to women on digital security, as well as to social workers and organisations supporting women. Likewise, guidelines can be provided for an adequate and ethical use of such tools.
- Support research on the specificities of digital forms of GBV.

5. GBV and public spaces

(For local authorities)

The pandemic and related policies such as lockdown and curfew have changed the ways in which GBV takes shape. For instance, it can take place in public spaces (transport, streets, etc.) that are emptier than usual. On the other hand, public spaces such as libraries or shops (e.g., pharmacies) have been useful information points or places to ask for help as showed above by the Mascarilla-19 initiative in Spain. Policies should explore the possibility to involve these spaces in their strategies to tackle GBV.

- Analyse urbanism with a gender perspective, with a view to carry out safety improvements in public spaces (e.g., remove black spots, improve lighting, safe transport system, etc.)
- Launch initiatives that involve public spaces and essential shops in delivering information and protocols to address requests for help and redirect victims to the designated services.

Telework as a double-edged sword: risks and opportunities

The COVID-19 crisis led to the rapid and widespread adoption of telework in a multitude of sectors to curb the spread of the virus, while also allowing organisations and companies to continue their activities. This sudden imposition of telework strongly impacted the relationships of people with regards to their jobs and their work-life balance, though these effects, both positive and negative, were not experienced in equal measure across all societal groups. However, while telework can, for instance, reinforce existing gender care and labour gaps, it can also serve as a catalyst for narrowing these gaps.

› *Background Information*

- The COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated the trend towards more teleworking. Teleworking can be beneficial by allowing more flexibility to workers and households: people can use their time more efficiently and reduce their time spent commuting, which, in turn, helps them achieve a better work-life balance. However, this doesn't necessarily apply to everyone and telework may not be in the best interest of some workers for a variety of reasons. For instance, telework can be challenging for employees because the boundaries between the professional sphere and the private sphere can become blurred. This leads to an increase in the number of working hours and difficulties for workers to disengage themselves from their professional responsibilities.
- The structural gender inequalities in the labour market have largely affected the unequal experience of teleworking between men and women. While more time at home might have made less involved caretakers (most often male partners) more aware of the importance of shared responsibilities within the household, the existing gender care gap in Europe meant that the immediate increased burden of care due to the movement restrictions almost exclusively fell on women. In addition to this, the gendered labour market segregation has crowded women's positions primarily in the care and hospitality sectors, which were hit the hardest during the pandemic-induced economic crisis, as well as the least able to transition online, meaning that women likely experienced the fewest gains from the telework transition.

› *Quantitative data: main findings*

Within the analysis of quantitative data from the RESISTIRÉ project¹, we have identified several examples of the dynamics described above, for instance: "*A French Rapid Assessment Survey (RAS) conducted among a representative sample of 2002 salaried*

office workers found that women were 1.3 times less likely than men to have an isolated space to work (62% compared to 71% of men) and 1.5 times more likely to be frequently interrupted when teleworking (28% compared to 19% for men)."

Regarding the gendered division of care/domestic work in light of new telework arrangements, the analysis of quantitative data found that "further research should investigate whether increased teleworking among fathers has had positive effects on norms and the gendered division of labour. National level RAS showed that fathers increased their contribution to childcare during the pandemic as a result of working from home."

While the forced, almost overnight shift to working from home has opened up new possibilities of organisational arrangements for working parents, it has also accentuated the already existing economic inequalities between women and men in Europe, and risks worsening them without the necessary systematic change that needs to happen alongside it.

› Narratives: main findings

Narratives collected by the RESISTIRÉ project² have indicated some examples of how the adoption of telework during the pandemic has impacted and continues to influence people's lives. Below are two examples:

GERMANY

A working middle-aged mother living in Germany (along with her husband) had to devote more time to taking care of her two small children when the pandemic started, since the children would normally spend two days per week with their grandparents. As a result, she had to work longer hours to be able to care for them during the day. Her employer granted everyone ten days of special leave, which was useful in the beginning, but what really helped was her husband being able to work from home – with the agreement of his employer – and sharing caretaking responsibilities. This allowed them to truly balance their domestic and care tasks.

“My husband has taken the liberty to work from home to take care of the children. (...) His employer played a huge role. This would not have been possible if his employer did not offer this flexibility.”

CYPRUS

“Another main problem I faced both during the lockdown and now, is my working condition. I have to telework since I cannot go to work due to my health problem. My employer was and still is ok with me teleworking. I managed to secure a laptop from my work during the first Covid wave, but it took months to get a printer at home.”

➤ *Better Stories*

Within RESISTIRE, we identify “Better Stories”, a term taken from Dina Georgis (2013) for promising practices that identify how a given societal situation can be ameliorated to improve existing practices.

- The Luxembourgish Ministry of Labour, Employment, and Social Economy introduced a voucher targeting workers in temporary (short-term) unemployment schemes that allows them to take part in online training courses to brush up on their digital skills. It covers up to €500 euros in costs and was specifically adopted to support workers impacted by the pandemic.
- In Belgium, a national interprofessional collective agreement instituted a number of stipulations with regards to telework (albeit only for a limited period of time). These stipulations ranged from the provision of equipment and technical support,

to the organisation of telework and working hours, to how employers may exercise control over their employees' work, among others.

>Recommendations

1. Unpaid Work is Work (See "Care and Crisis" factsheet)

The increased prevalence of telework provides an opportunity to improve the general position of women in the labour market. In this regard, however, it is crucial to recognise unpaid work as work, to allow sufficient time for unpaid work when an employee works from home, and to actively fight gender stereotypes in order to ensure that women – who bear the brunt of unpaid domestic & care labour – do not see this burden increase and to help enable a closing of the gender care gap. It is essential for policies

to incentivise a more equitable distribution of caring duties and a fairer division of labour when working from home in order for telework to have a positive impact on gender equality. A number of hours of required care/domestic work during the day could be recognised as part of the working hours for every employee working remotely, outlined within the framework of a telework arrangement (as recommended above). Furthermore, men could be actively encouraged and incentivised to make use of this arrangement so that traditional gender roles are not reinforced. Policies like these, that trust employees and recognise the role of care work in day-to-day life, can actually create more equitable household divisions of labour and, potentially, push for cultural change around the issue of care work.

2. Right to Flexible Telework

Because telework might not be in all employees' best interests, the workers' right to voluntary telework should be guaranteed, and the concrete implementation of this right should be safeguarded through a legal and regulatory framework. To account for differences in teleworkability in different sectors, the legal framework could be arranged through collective bargaining agreements on a sectoral level. This would also ensure that telework becomes accessible to all workers, in some way or form, and prevent

new inequalities from taking root.

3. Right to Disconnect

The 'right to disconnect' outside of working hours should fall under the fundamental principle of occupational health and safety for workers. The existence of this right should be clearly communicated and employers should encourage their employees to make use of it, in order to ensure a better work-life balance and greater productivity during working hours. Clear rules on when workers are expected to be online and available for collaborative work should be established and respected, as well as the freedom of workers to organise their work and their working hours as best fits their schedule. The concept of 'core hours', i.e., hours during which meetings and workshops can be organised and during which employees should be available for teleconferences and (video) calls, can serve as an inspiring example of good teleworking etiquette.

4. Telework is Work: Worker's Occupational Health and Safety

While teleworking, workers are still performing their professional activities. As such, all occupational health and safety regulations should apply as much at home (or when working from another remote location) as in the traditional workplace. The same principle holds for all other labour rights enshrined in law. The prevention of potential negative side-effects of telework on employees' physical and mental health therefore remains the responsibility of the employer.

5. Telework is a New Kind of Work: Creating a Culture of Trust and Support

A successful telework arrangement depends on an adapted approach to work by the employer. Overly controlling and monitoring working relationships present a detriment to the well-being and health of workers, as well as to their overall productivity. As such, a style of leadership that is based on support and trust between employers and employees, rather than one based on control, is essential. Concretely, the employer should adjust the expected working hours and productivity standards. Currently, teleworkers work longer hours than when they work in the workplace, while at the same time increasing their self-monitoring and putting more pressure on themselves than necessary or required. Therefore, employers should openly discuss with their employees about the expectations that exist with regards to remote work (i.e., how much work is expected of workers within a given timeframe). Allowing and encouraging employee input in the organisation of telework is absolutely crucial to ensure that a successful teleworking arrangement is put in place and adhered to. If done correctly and in a clear manner telework can be very beneficial to both employers and employees.

Pilot Projects

Selection and Development

The Open Studios resulted in twenty action-ideas that could potentially become pilot projects. Out of these twenty, a selection of the most promising action-ideas was needed, based on the following criteria:

- The innovative nature of the action
- The potential impact
- The potential to attract attention and awareness
- The practical feasibility, including for example the estimated budget, the possibility to find an organisation to execute the project, etc.

To create the shortlist, YW led a process of deliberation within the consortium. First, a longlist of twenty action-ideas was communicated to the task leaders in WP6, namely K&I, ORU and ISAS. This was quickly followed by a proposed shortlist by YW, which was also sent to the SU team, who were involved during the Open Studios and could provide valuable feedback.

The preliminary shortlist that was agreed upon, based on the criteria mentioned above, contained five potential pilot projects: Increase voice of migrant workforce with an irregular work status, Caring Workplace, Platform for digital training for women, Green spaces as ecosystems of care, and Municipalities for developing holistic care for healthcare workers.

The five potential pilot projects were then elaborated upon based on the input from the Open Studios, and afterwards shared with the consortium for feedback. Consortium partners had the opportunity to add important information, such as relevant organisations that could execute the projects, as well as their own interest in leading the design of the projects and issuing the call.

Finally, three action-ideas received the most support from the consortium to be developed further into pilot projects: 1) Increase voice of migrant workforce with an irregular work status; 2) Green spaces as ecosystems of care; 3) Caring Workplace. Despite only envisaging two pilot projects at this stage, it was decided that all three should be taken up further, after which a final review would decide whether to continue with all three, or with two.

A lead was appointed to develop each action into guidelines for applicants. The lead was supported throughout the whole development process by a core group of contributors

from the partners. K&I and YW, as task leader and WP leader respectively, were part of all core groups. Once the first drafts of the guidelines were finalised, they were tested with at least two organisations knowledgeable on the subject, that provided additional feedback and comments, which were subsequently incorporated. Table 3 shows the titles of the pilot projects, as well as the main partner responsible and the organisation that tested the concept.

Table 3 – Pilot Projects

Pilot Project	Responsible Partner	Test
Employers Who Care	UDEUSTO	Spanish Municipality, Italian and Spanish NGO, expert from Spain
Green Spaces as Caring Ecosystems	YW	Belgian and Italian NGO
Caring Workplace	SU	Commercial bank in Ireland and expert from Turkey

The deadline to finalise the guidelines was set on the 19th of November. A public call will subsequently be opened on the website from the end of November, that will remain open until mid-January. In January the selection process will take place, and the pilot projects will start from the 7th of February.

In what follows, we will provide an overview and the contents of the three pilot projects: Employers Who Care, Green Spaces as Caring Ecosystems and Caring Workplace.

Pilot Project 1 – Employers Who Care

Background

The COVID-19 crisis has emphasized the importance of care work in all its shapes, urging the need to improve working conditions, tackle precariousness and recognise decent salaries. However, the attention has mostly focused on institutionalised healthcare workers (healthcare professionals in hospitals and residences), neglecting once again the working conditions of the most marginalised and vulnerable care workers, those working in private households. This group has also been at the frontline and suffered extremely the consequences of the pandemic.

A great proportion of domestic workers (employed in tasks such as cleaning the house, cooking, taking care of children, elderly or sick members of a family) in Europe are women of migrant origin, sometimes with no regular residence permit and/or with no regular contract. Even in situations of regular contract, working conditions are often precarious, with regulations that allow insufficient or low protection. Following the pandemic

outbreak, many domestic workers lost their employment, had no access to unemployment benefits, or were trapped into the employer's house (live-in domestic workers), even exposed to aggressions and violence. In some cases, live-in domestic workers who lost their jobs ended up in the street.

In this context, many actors are involved in the transformation of the homecare sector, such as public administrations, civil society organisations, unions and domestic workers themselves. An increasing number of domestic workers have organised among themselves, establishing associations and unions to campaign for their rights across Europe and to build support networks. Likewise, many organisations across Europe have launched initiatives that focus on empowering and offering training to migrant women, sometimes targeting domestic workers specifically. In some cases, municipalities have even set up offices that provide information and support related to domestic work.

While much still needs to be done to reach and support domestic workers, there is also the need and the opportunity to reach the employers (both individuals and families) as the other party in the employment relationship. Employers are regarded in this pilot project as key actors for a sustainable change in the homecare sector. Their involvement is fundamental to improve the working conditions as well as to contribute to the recognition of care work as valuable.

The ultimate goal of this pilot action is the improvement of working conditions, understood not only as compliance with the minimum legal requirements but also as fostering a better working environment, based on mutual understanding, equality and fairness.

Domestic workers, mostly migrant women nowadays, are the ultimate beneficiaries of this pilot action. By involving them, their voices will also be strengthened. Employers would benefit from this project both in terms of having more satisfied employees and more stable and lasting employment relationships and in terms of contributing to the creation of more just employment relationships.

Objectives

The overall objective of this pilot project is to contribute to the positive transformation of the homecare sector and the working conditions of domestic workers by mobilising "committed" employers as key actors of change and as allies of domestic workers.

More specifically, the pilot project has four main specific objectives:

1. To **mobilise employers** of domestic workers (individuals and/or families) as actors for change;
2. To **raise awareness** among employers of the rights, circumstances and needs of domestic workers and of the importance of acting as allies;
3. To **promote alliances** among grassroots organisations and to **strengthen the**

voices of migrant women domestic workers;

4. To **disseminate** the process and outcomes to raise awareness among the general public and other employers.

Description and Methodology

The core idea of this pilot project is to focus on employers as actors of change and allies of domestic workers, in the process of recognising domestic work as a valuable, essential occupation that needs adequate recognition and substantive improvements. To this end, this pilot project seeks to gather those committed employers that could participate in the change, by enhancing their sense of social responsibility and sensitivity towards domestic work. This pilot project seeks to build on that sense of solidarity that emerged during the pandemic and consolidate it as a factor of change and social cohesion.

This call is issued to non-governmental organisations and/or associations that engage with networks of domestic workers and networks of employers. Within the RESISTIRÉ project, we recognise that the voices and agency of domestic workers (individually and collectively) remain at the core of this social struggle and should gain visibility. For this reason, the whole process of design and implementation of awareness-raising activities should be based on a bottom-up approach. In this sense, the ability to connect and involve different representatives and stakeholders will be key.

The expected tasks are the following (organised by objective):

1. To develop a **network of private employers** (individuals and/or families) who support change and are willing to create synergies:
 - a. To **identify and involve** a number of employers that are willing to participate in the activities. The employers will generally be reached using the network of the implementing organisation.
 - b. To **set up a platform** (e.g., Facebook group, Telegram or WhatsApp group) or an equivalent way to channel the communication, information and discussion among the employers. The platform could be used to share reflections, ask questions and expose difficulties that could be addressed through the project.
2. To **design and implement** activities among the network of employers:
 - a. To develop and implement a **programme** of activities to raise awareness on areas such as:
 - i. rights and obligations related to employment relationship beyond the often inadequate or discriminatory legal framework already in place;
 - ii. strategies to develop more equal and fair labour relationships, based on empathy and solidarity;
 - iii. understand the needs and difficulties that domestic workers face due to overlapping inequalities;

- iv. debunk harmful stereotypes based on gender and race/migration, among others.
- b. To develop and implement activities to **explore better stories/promising practices** from employers. These would include ways to support domestic workers, ways to improve the working conditions, in the broad sense, of domestic workers, and strategies and possible actions to act as allies.

Activities implemented within this programme should incorporate a gender sensitive and intersectional approach. They should be carried out through methodologies and techniques that foster participation, inclusion and that are set up in a safe environment, accessible to all as much as possible. Additionally, they could explore the possibility of using artistic means (theatre, poetry, role play, etc.) to convey empathy and generate knowledge.

3. To set up a **team of facilitators** to carry out the activities:
 - a. To **map** the different stakeholders at the local and/or regional level, mainly grassroots organisations (e.g., women's networks and associations focusing on migrants 'rights) with first-hand experience with the homecare sector and its challenges, as well as existing networks of employers.
 - b. To **involve** some of the organisations and actors as facilitators of the activities. The composition of the team would ensure strengthening the alliances between social partners and foster a sustainable impact for the pilot. Care workers should be actively involved in the activities, by sharing their experiences. This would contribute to increasing their voices and recognising their agency.
4. To carry out **dissemination and awareness raising actions** towards society in general:

A set of dissemination and awareness-raising actions targeting society at large should be conducted through different channels, involving as many and as various stakeholders as possible, such as different members of civil society and public authorities at the local or regional level. Expected actions would be, among other, a campaign on social media and an event to present the outcomes of the project. The aim of such actions would be twofold: on the one hand, to raise awareness among society at large and different stakeholders of the importance of the issue; on the other, to make the outcomes available and known to other employers and potential employers.

Dissemination and awareness actions will be created by the selected candidate by leveraging their network and channels. They will be shared with RESISTIRÉ's social media accounts. The content will include full acknowledgement of the RESISTIRÉ project and link to the outputs on the RESISTIRÉ website.

Required Outcomes

1. A **network of employers** set up through social media/website/other, which is sustainable through time (15-20 participants).
 - 2.1. A set of **activities** to raise awareness have been carried out with employers, to equip them with knowledge and tools on how to contribute to change.
 - 2.2. A set of **good practices** for developing more ethical working relationships in the private care sector is developed and shared with other potential employers and employer organisations, and to raise awareness among society.
3. **Dialogue and exchange** among the different actors (e.g., employers' network and organisations, associations and representatives of domestic care workers) has been fostered through the activities implemented, and **empowerment** of domestic workers has increased through their involvement in the activities facilitated.
4. **Increased social awareness** on the inequalities faced by domestic workers among society, as well as on ways to act as an ally following a set of best practices, among employers and potential employers. Social media activity and events have been organised to raise awareness and attract potential participants and future agents of change.

Territorial Scope

Due to the limited timeframe and budget allocated to this action, the pilot project should be implemented at the **local or regional level in one of the eligible countries** (EU27+ UK, Serbia, Iceland, and Turkey).

Timeframe

The pilot project should start in March 2022 and the foreseen end is October 2022. An example of a general work schedule for the implementation of the project could be organised as follows:

Months 1 to 3 / March, April, and May

- Reach employers and involve them in a network
- Build or further alliances with different organisations and stakeholders
- Design a programme of activities
- Set up a team of facilitators
- Campaign and dissemination activities

Months 4 to 7 / June, July, August and September

- Implement the activities with the employers
- Continuously update the campaign and dissemination activities
- Monitor activities internally

Months 8 / October

- Final reporting

Applicant organisations will be asked to provide a detailed work schedule of activities.

Risks and How to Mitigate Them

Alongside the risks listed below, the selected organisation can identify and point to others during the course of the project, and provide relevant mitigation strategies where capable.

Risks:

1. Risk of not reaching the target (employers). To mitigate this, the applicant is expected to have a solid network of contacts and to be embedded in the local community. Reaching out to potential members of the network will be facilitated by this.
2. Risk of not establishing a constructive dialogue and on equal footing in the activities with employers, facilitated by organisations or representatives of domestic care workers. In particular, it is important to be aware of potential conflicts of interest between employers and domestic care workers. In this sense, specific care will need to be taken in the activities proposed to ensure a safe and inclusive environment for all participants. Stress will be put on potential room for improvement of the working conditions, in a constructive manner. In order to remove potential barriers to interactions between peers, it is not expected that employers and their direct employees participate in this dialogue together.
3. Short timeframe to implement the action (6 months). The number of tasks is clearly identified, to facilitate their completion in time.

Pilot Project 2 – Green Spaces as Caring Ecosystems

Background

The COVID-19 pandemic confirmed the contribution that green spaces make to the wellbeing of those living in residential communities. At the same time, it also highlighted how access to green spaces is conditioned by multiple intersecting inequality factors, such as gender, social class, socioeconomic status and ethnicity. Moreover, although a green space is a positive element that all members of the surrounding community are theoretically able to enjoy, it may at the same time attract some people but exclude those who do not perceive the area as a place that can meet their needs.

A green space consists of "hardware" - the green space itself and all its structures

including public furniture, sports facilities, etc - but also of "software", which represents the different ways in which the space is used. This project idea puts the focus on the software side of green spaces, more specifically the programming of the use of the different areas of the space, of the different infrastructures available, the timing of the use and who is using the space. By focusing on the software side, different programmes could be implemented and adapted in a participatory way, considering the needs of all and especially of vulnerable groups in the area.

The programmes could promote inclusiveness and contribute to developing the green space as an 'Ecosystem of Care', which can be seen as an expansion of the 'home realm'. There, problems and care needs can be addressed outside the home with the help of the community. In this context, the term 'Ecosystem of Care' includes not only the care of the individual, but recognises and cares for groups that are typically discouraged from frequenting green spaces. An 'Ecosystem of Care' also addresses the natural inhabitants of green spaces and embraces the need to protect wildlife. Finally, it also refers to democratic care and conflict resolution.

The utilisation of green spaces as 'Ecosystems of Care' enables the modification and evolution of these spaces, and ensures that the purposes of green spaces can change with the needs of surrounding and connected user groups.

Objectives

The overall objective of this pilot project is to transform green spaces into an 'Ecosystem of Care' through the development and implementation of programmes that make all users, and in particular vulnerable groups (from a gender+ perspective), feel welcome and able to access green spaces. More specifically, the pilot project has three main specific objectives:

1. For one specific green space: to **identify** the diverse community members who could use them, and to identify their respective needs;
2. To **formulate an agenda/plan**, based on the above findings, that provides a clear programme of activities for the local community, especially people from vulnerable groups;
3. To **implement, communicate and evaluate** this plan to assess its strengths and weaknesses, measure the increased use by vulnerable groups, as well as capture feedback from community members.

Description and Methodology

To more adequately engage communities around a green space, the green space should be programmed to a degree that attracts various groups of people, but does not exclude potential users either. This call is issued to social organisations experienced in contacting, working, and interacting with all kinds of people and (their) local communities, especially those in vulnerable groups. The organisation should be able to organise regular activities

in a particular green space. These activities would transform the green space into a welcome and inclusive area. Particular attention should be paid to the role of care in this process: one of the ways in which this project tries to create more inclusive green spaces, is to address the issues people are facing in a collective and holistic way, thereby creating a caring environment and strengthening local ties and solidarity. The project should make use of a participatory approach, meaning that the programming should be inspired by and based on the involvement and contributions of local communities and users of the space.

The expected tasks are as follows (organised by objective):

1. To **identify** a green space and its users:
 - a. To **find** a suitable green space and a municipality that is willing to allow the project to take place;
 - b. To **conduct research** into the demographic make-up of (potential) users of the identified green space and to pinpoint the needs, wants and interests of these (potential) users. Special attention should be paid to overlapping and conflicting needs, and strategies should be developed to resolve any conflicts that could arise.
 - c. **Building alliances of care** within and through the green space that connect people from diverse backgrounds with each other and promote solidarity and mutual aid. This is done by identifying suitable organisations and (potential) community organisers who can incorporate the green space into their activities and by connecting them with each other (i.e., schools, clubs, associations, local companies, etc.)
2. To **program** a selected green space by:
 - a. **Developing and publishing a programme** that lays out an agenda of activities for the green space (comparable with programmes of, i.e., cultural institutions) and takes into account the existing uses and users, as well as the various care needs of a more diverse group of users, especially those of vulnerable groups. This should be done through a bottom-up approach that involves local organisations, individuals, and other actors. Care should be taken to allow for “silent” areas that are not actively programmed, so that people can still enjoy calmer environments;
3. To **carry out the programme** by:
 - a. **Setting up a “board”** of users (or equivalent governance) that meets regularly to discuss and formally approve the programme in a democratic manner. Potential members of the board are identified from the alliances of care set up in the previous steps.
 - b. **Implementing** the programme by engaging the aforementioned local organisations, individuals, and other actors, **carrying out the minor structural interventions** needed to accommodate all kinds of users.

- c. [In parallel with b.] **Stimulating the use** of the green space by launching a **promotion campaign** to communicate the existence and benefits of the programme to (potential) users in the vicinity of the green space;
- d. **Final reporting** on the practical implementation of the programme to identify the increased use of the space and by whom, the overall effectiveness, potential areas that could be improved, and problems to be solved.

Required Outcomes

1. A programme of green space activities is provided, able to attract a diverse range of users from the local community,
2. Vulnerable groups (from a gender+ perspective) are specifically targeted and involved in the programming of the space and in the creation of new social networks.
3. The surrounding areas are positively affected in terms of inclusiveness, participation, collaboration and solidarity. The local community is reinforced and durable social networks are built.

Territorial Scope

Due to the limited timeframe and budget allocated to this action, the pilot project should be implemented at the **local (municipality) level** in **one of the eligible countries** (EU27+ UK, Serbia, Iceland, and Turkey).

Timeframe

The pilot project should be started in February 2022 and the foreseen end is August 2022. It is required that the actual realisation of the programme last no less than three/four months. A general work schedule for the implementation of the project could be organised as follows:

Months 1 to 3 / February, March and April

- Carry out research on the demographic composition of (potential) users
- Build alliances of care
- Set up a “board” of users
- Develop and publish a programme
- Launch the promotion campaign

Months 4 to 7 / May, June, July and August

- Implement the programme
- Continuously update the promotional campaign
- Monitor activities internally

Months 8 / September

- Final reporting

Applicant organisations will be asked to provide a detailed work schedule of activities.

Risks and How to Mitigate Them

Alongside the risks listed below, the selected organisation can identify and point to others during the course of the project, and provide relevant mitigation strategies where capable.

Risks:

1. The need to cooperate with a municipality or other green space owner entails some risks. A municipality can 'change its mind' and decide to stop cooperating. On the other hand, it can also get too involved in the project, trying to interfere with what should be a bottom-up approach. To avoid situations like this, a clear (written) agreement with conditions should be negotiated and signed by both parties within the first month of project implementation.
2. The selected organisation should avoid getting involved in the concrete organisation of the planned activities themselves, but should stick to its programming responsibility. The activities should be carried out by users and other organisations who express interest in being involved in the project (identified through the alliances of care), i.e., schools, local sports facilities, (small) businesses, families, associations, informal groups. Clear boundaries on what tasks the organisation will and will not be involved in should be communicated to these interested parties.
3. Conflicts over green space use with existing users and/or uses. Again, making sure that local organisations and communities are involved is crucial, so as to avoid and/or resolve any conflicting views on how areas of the green space should be programmed and utilised.

Pilot Project 3 – Caring Workplaces

Background

The COVID-19 pandemic has redefined the way people work. It has increased pressures on frontline workers and contributed to the restructuring of employment relationships

through the spreading of telework. All these shifts have highlighted the need for more caring workspaces that value the diverse skills of the workforce and provide for an inclusive environment for its employees.

On one hand, the pandemic has created an opportunity for redefining the meaning of essential work and essential skills, as the work of healthcare and care workers (a sector over-represented by women) drew attention to the central role of emotional labour, emotional intelligence, and skills such as flexibility, empathy and resilience -rarely recognised as essential or as part of the promotion process.

these different life domains.

On the other hand, the unprecedented rise in telework, along with the closure of schools and childcare facilities during lockdowns, contributed to the further blurring of the boundaries between the private sphere and the sphere of paid work and put an excessive pressure on many working parents. This highlights the significance for a workspace which recognizes the importance of work-life balance and calls for a greater understanding of the relationship between

In essence, caring workspaces provide employees and employers with multiple benefits, including an increase in the well-being of workers, a reduction of psycho-social risks at the workplace, a reduction in absenteeism and sick leaves, increased levels of creativity and greater sense of belonging and solidarity among employees.

Objectives

“There is always a better story than the better story.”
(Dina Georgis (2013), 2013)

This pilot action is about co-creating the “better story” of a caring gender+ workspace that is inclusive, diverse and safe for employees at all levels, while also responding to the new challenges posed by the pandemic and the increase in teleworking.

More specifically, the pilot project aims at:

- re-imagining organisational culture and the working environment as inclusive, diverse, safe and caring, where everyone's unique contribution and creativity is

- recognised and rewarded from a gender+ perspective;
- supporting the creation of a greater sense of community, connection, belonging, collegiality, and solidarity among members of an organisation;
- developing organisational schemes for better work-life balance;
- encouraging employers to recognise versatile skill-sets, developing modalities of emotional labour to be recognised as a skill in the workspace;
- promoting organisational schemes that respond to the physical and mental health needs of all employees;
- mitigating old/new psycho-social risks and contribute to organisational and work safety (less lost workdays due to psycho-somatic or psycho-social risks).

Description and Methodology

The specific tasks that the applicant is expected to perform are as follows:

- 1) **To conduct desk research** to collect existing better stories in terms of inclusive, diverse, safe and caring workspaces, implemented by organisations at national and European levels,
- 2) **To co-create** (with partners from multiple sectors, disciplines and areas) a **comprehensive checklist** for an inclusive, diverse, safe and caring workspace from a gender+ perspective, including the challenges of teleworking,
- 3) **To identify at least two organisations** (preferably from different sectors, including NGOs, trade unions, universities, public institutions, municipalities, and corporations) that are willing to engage in a co-creative process, for further developing the checklist and implementing it within the organisation,
- 4) **To launch an open call on social media**, involving organisations implementing promising practices all over Europe (including those identified during the desk research phase) for an award titled “Better story of caring workspaces”.
- 5) **To set up a communication campaign to:**
 - create a public discussion and raise awareness on the significance and potentialities of inclusive, diverse, safe and caring workspaces, inviting the general public to suggest additional items to the checklist,
 - gather input from the general public to explore different visions of an inclusive, diverse, safe and caring workspace,
 - disseminate the call for the award titled “Better stories of caring workspaces”,
 - invite public participation to vote for the award,
 - give visibility to the better stories of caring workspaces in a variety of sectors and contexts across Europe.

The campaign will be led through social media and in-person presentations in events. The

social media campaign will be created by the selected candidate leverage on their own network and channels. It will be shared with RESISTIRÉ's social media accounts. The content will include full acknowledgement of the RESISTIRÉ project and link to outputs on RESISTIRE's website.

A gender+/intersectional approach will be systematically integrated in all the activities of the pilot action. Participatory methods are deployed in the implementation of its tasks. The pilot action, including its social media campaign, is delivered through an open-ended co-creation process involving key stakeholders and the general public in order to enable a sense of "shared ownership" throughout.

Required Outcomes

1. A checklist for a caring workspace is co-created with participants from different sectors and disciplines (including NGOs, trade unions, universities, public institutions, municipalities, and corporations) and promoted to as many public and private bodies as possible, as well as the general public, to raise awareness.
2. Implementation in at least two organisations of a checklist or a charter for an inclusive, diverse, safe and caring workspace, tailoring some of its contents to the peculiarities of their sector and their type of organisation; feedback from employers at all levels is collected.
3. An award to select the "Better stories of caring workspaces" is advertised extensively (reaching 150+ organisations) and assigned.
4. A charter (also in the form of an infographic) including the basic principles of a caring workspace is co-created with the involved participants from different sectors and disciplines, based on the results of checklist implementation and the general experience of the project.
5. A dissemination campaign promoting inclusive, diverse, safe and caring workspaces and better stories is launched and maintained, through in-person presentations and a social media campaign (including diverse channels and creative communication materials, such as short videos, media posts with photos and infographics, strong engagement with high-reach accounts). A total of 10K profile/website visits reached, from various target audiences (general public, NGOs, policymakers, employers)

Territorial Scope

The successful applicant is expected to be based in one of the countries involved in the RESISTIRÉ project (EU27+ Turkey, Serbia, Iceland and the UK).

It is expected that (at least two) organisations from the same country as the successful applicant engage in a co-creative process to further develop and implement the checklist for an inclusive, diverse, safe and caring workspace are based in.

It is recommended that the desk research, the social media campaign and the award announcement will cover as many countries involved in the RESISTIRÉ project as possible (EU27+ Turkey, Serbia, Iceland and the UK).

Timeframe

The pilot project should be started in March 2022 and the foreseen end is November 2022. A general work schedule for the implementation of the project could be organised as follows:

Months 1 and 2 / March and April

- Carry out desk research to collect existing initiatives and promising practices in terms of inclusive, diverse, safe and caring workspaces, implemented by organisations at national and European level
- Identify (at least) two organisations willing to engage in the further development and implementation of the checklist for an inclusive, diverse, safe and caring workspace

Months 3 and 4 / May and June

- Co-create (with partners from multiple sectors, disciplines and areas) a comprehensive checklist for an inclusive, diverse, safe and caring workspace from a gender+ perspective, including the challenges of teleworking
- Design, launch and implement the social media campaign
- (At least two identified organisations) further develop and start implementing the checklist for an inclusive, diverse, safe and caring workspace

Months 5 / July

- The open call titled “Better stories of caring workspaces” is launched and open to collect applications
- Interim reporting (including desk research results)

Months 5, 6 and 7 / July, August and September

- The social media campaign is active and covers all point under task 5)
- (At least two identified organisations) keep on implementing the checklist for an inclusive, diverse, safe and caring workspace

Months 8 / October

- The open call titled “Better stories of inclusive, diverse, safe and caring workspace” closes and the award is assigned
- The social media campaign is active and covers all point under task 5)
- (At least two identified organisations) keep on implementing the checklist for an inclusive, diverse, safe and caring workspace

Months 9 / November

- The final version of the checklist is released
- The charter defining the meaning and basic principles of a caring workspace is released
- The applicant collects feedback from the (at least) two identified organizations' employers at all levels; feedback is processed in a report.

Month 10 / December

- Final reporting

Applicant organisations will be asked to provide a detailed work schedule of activities.

Risks and How to Mitigate Them

Alongside the risks listed below, the selected organisation can identify and point to others during the course of the project, and provide relevant mitigation strategies where capable.

- Risks associated with partnership: one risk is that it will be difficult to involve other organisations in the project. The solution is to identify partners for this pilot project in advance and include their expression of interest letters in the application for the call.
- Risks associated with originality: checklists and awards already exist. The solution is to focus on gaps that can be filled, such as gender+ and cross-sectoral aspects, accessibility of these tools and social awareness (social media campaign as one of the solutions).
- Risks associated with enforcement: there are existing regulations, checklists etc, but these are not always enforced or followed by employers. The social media campaign could be part of the solution to this issue.

Agenda for Future Research

The aim of the research agenda is to identify knowledge gaps and formulate future research needs to understand/mitigate/eradicate behavioral, social, and economic inequalities produced by the policy responses to COVID-19. The purpose is to identify knowledge gaps for future research agendas, and to inform the research questions that will be taken up in the next cycle. Particular attention is paid to the overarching research related aims of the project:

- Investigate and analyze the impact of COVID-19 and of different policies developed by both the public and private sector on inequalities, and understand the role of civil society in mitigating these inequalities.
- Identify and compare in which domains there are positive/negative COVID-19 impacts, for which gender+ inequality groups, and how these may be impacted by policy.
- Identify knowledge gaps on how inequalities play out and develop during outbreak periods.

The findings produced by RESISTIRE during the research phase are based on the analysis of various empirical data collected and analyzed in different work-packages: the mapping of Policies/CSO initiatives; official secondary data sources at the international and EU level, as well as RAS at the national level; expert interviews/workshops; and narratives from members of vulnerable groups. In the research agenda these findings have been synthesized in order to identify what knowledge is currently missing in order to support further research aimed at improving the development and implementation of covid induced policies/responses considering their impacts on vulnerable groups and (pre)existing inequalities.

In the following section, the report will first provide an overview of the research agenda for four domains that were identified during the project. These domains are: Care, Work & Pay, Human Rights and Health and Gender-based Violence. For each domain, main findings from the first cycle are highlighted, as well as knowledge gaps identified based on the empirical data collection and analysis, and potential research questions. The research agenda of RESISTIRÉ's second cycle is provided in a second stage.

Research Agenda per Domain

Knowledge Gaps and Research Questions Related to Care

Care work can be broadly defined as the activity of providing personal services to meet the physical, psychological, and emotional needs of one or more other persons (EIGE, 2021a; ILO, 2007). Care work can be done visibly – institutionalised as paid employment

– or invisibly, in the home (ILO, 2007). The quantitative mapping performed by RESISTIRÉ focuses on the latter, given that the visibility of unpaid care work performed in the home increased exponentially during the pandemic crisis (Rubery and Tavora, 2020).

The effect of the pandemic on women’s care responsibilities and on women’s work, work-life balance and mental health

The findings from the first cycle of RESISTIRÉ indicate that there appears to be a link between the burden of childcare and a decrease in working hours during the pandemic. In most of the countries mapped, a higher share of working women living with children under 18 reported that their working hours had decreased substantially, compared to men living with children of the same age and working women without dependent children. Decreased working hours may indicate an increased uptake of part-time work as opposed to full-time employment. Many of the reviewed RAS indicated that women took on the majority of care responsibilities and were particularly burdened with home-schooling. The RAS also suggested that care responsibilities increased during the pandemic due to the loss of formal and informal support, such as support services for disabled people, homecare for older adults and childcare offered by grandparents and friends.

This increased care burden has had consequences for women’s well-being. Studies find that the pandemic had a greater impact on women’s mental health than men’s and that, compared to men, women felt more overwhelmed, exhausted and stressed and less satisfied with work, family life and life in general. Several studies suggest that women’s poorer mental health outcomes are directly linked to the gender care gap and mothers in particular were found to suffer. In sum, the burden of women’s care responsibilities seems to be associated with negative consequences on women’s performance at work, their work-life balance and their mental health. Currently, the findings show that there are no comparable data at the European level on time spent on housework and childcare pre- and post-pandemic.

There is an overall research gap concerning the long-term effects of the increased care responsibilities during the pandemic on women’s (in all their diversity) participation in paid work and the effects on their health.

Research Questions:

- How have the increasing care responsibilities during the pandemic affected women’s work patterns and what long-term consequences may this have for women’s possibilities to secure working conditions, career development and economic security from a life cycle perspective?
- How have the increased care responsibilities during the pandemic affected women’s well-being and mental health?

The effect of the pandemic on men's care responsibilities and the masculinisation of care work

A steep rise in the prevalence of home working during the pandemic is likely to have increased the opportunities for fathers to be involved in childcare, with possible lasting effects on gender norms and the gendered division of labour. Many RAS show that a substantial number of fathers increased their contribution to childcare during the pandemic due to remote working, which led to greater flexibility in work hours and reduced commute times. However, the RAS overwhelmingly indicate that women still took on the majority of care responsibilities and were particularly burdened with home-schooling. In sum, the pandemic has increased the time that some men spend on household/domestic tasks, with potential effects on their care responsibilities and the masculinisation of care work.

There is an overall research gap related to the changing role of men (in all their diversity) and masculinity relations with regards to care responsibilities pre-, during and post-pandemic.

Research Questions:

- What short-term and long-term effects has increased remote working among fathers had on gender norms and the gendered division of care labour?
- What effects have the increased care responsibilities of men had on their work and health?
- What effects have the increased care responsibilities of men had on their family relations?

A re-traditionalisation of care responsibilities, intersectional perspectives and the effects for an equal division of care work

The analysis of national RAS has indicated that women have taken up more of the additional unpaid work and childcare than men, thus exacerbating existing gender inequalities. These results indicate the risk of a re-traditionalisation of gender roles with regards to care responsibilities, one example being young women and girls living at home that have increased their participation in care work. A number of RAS pointed to additional childcare and home-schooling responsibilities being more of a struggle for single-parent families, families with several children, families with low incomes and families where parents had lower levels of education. Some RAS indicated that less-educated women were disproportionately hit by the unequal division of household chores and faced mutually reinforcing barriers (low labour force participation, limited social protection coverage, and more stringent traditional gender norms). However, contrasting findings were observed in other national research, which found that a gender care gap was particularly observed among middle-class, highly educated city-dwelling women.

The collected narratives indicated that women have engaged in more intense care-work

of those who are the most care-dependent. The focus on gender, class, disability, and age in the narratives concerning the gender care gap, also means that there are important knowledge gaps in these domains. Considering the number of migrant care workers in Europe, the narratives contain few experiences of how care is linked to race/ethnicity and nationality. Moreover, due to the focus on care in relation to heterosexual coupledness, narratives on how care is linked to sexuality and gender identity are missing.

In sum, the findings indicate a re-traditionalisation of gender roles associated with care responsibilities and that the division of care responsibilities is influenced by intersectional gendered causes. The findings indicate a lack of data to conduct analysis of the intersections between the gender care gap and inequalities relating to race/ethnicity, nationality, sexuality and gender identity. Therefore, there is an overall research gap related to the short- and long-term effects on intersectional gendered norms and behaviours associated with care responsibilities.

Research Questions:

- What long-term effects will the widening care gap during the pandemic have for the division of unpaid care work post-pandemic from a gender perspective?
- How have the increasing care responsibilities during the pandemic affected women and men from an intersectional perspective, such as for young single mothers and fathers, elderly women and men caring for younger and older dependent others, people in different geographical locations and from differing socio-economic backgrounds?

The effect of changing care patterns during the pandemic on those who are dependent on care

Results show that inequalities have not only widened in terms of the provision of unpaid care, but also that the pandemic has had an effect on the recipients of care. Effects relate to both changes in the type of care needed and in the ways in which people are able to receive care. People who are particularly dependent on the care from others, such as people with disabilities and or very young/old people, have been severely impacted during the pandemic, and have often experienced precarity.

More research is necessary related to how the pandemic has affected receivers of informal and unpaid care work on a short term and long-term perspective.

Research Questions:

- How have patterns in the provision and care needs changed during the pandemic and to what effects for those groups that are depended on informal/unpaid care?

The lack of an equality perspective in pandemic policymaking and the effects on inequalities

Current policies relating to the domain of care work highlight how, from the beginning of the pandemic to the present day, the priority has been the maintenance of economic activity, while only occasionally trying to mitigate the problems that emerged in the management of care activities. Consequently, the underlying causes of the gender care gap in general have not been addressed.

One of the main issues is that in general, policies have only indirectly considered women. They have done so by building on stereotypical gender assumptions that assign the caregiver role to women. Even in countries that have long been devoted to a dual-earner model, where care activities are mostly outsourced outside the family context, gender inequality in care activities was quickly re-established by the crisis. Therefore, while most policies introduced to support care activities helped a portion of women to maintain an income and not lose their jobs, they also contributed to reinforcing gender stereotypes that see women as the primary or sole caregivers. This has reinforced the broader trend of more women taking up unpaid care work. Thus, such measures have also often had the effect of increasing the unpaid care work burden on women, leading to reduced income and increased risk of poverty, especially for single mothers and women in low-income categories.

Additionally, a lack of gender+ sensitivity in these policies can be observed. Measures are heteronormative and usually refer to fathers and mothers. Furthermore, the access criteria of the anti-crisis measures penalised specific categories of people, such as people with flexible or precarious contracts, parents of children in age groups not considered by the measures, and people not registered through social insurance. In most cases measures do not take into consideration all the informal relations that exist (e.g., those not defined by contracts, citizenship, family relations).

There is an overall research gap related to why equality perspectives have been absent in pandemic policy making. There are variations in the findings, but the results indicate the gender composition in policy making and the non-involvement of experts and consultation with civil society as having an impact. Furthermore, information best practices regarding how public authorities, educational institutions, and workplaces have supported carers combining paid and unpaid care-work during the pandemic is scarce and should be mapped.

Research Questions:

- Have the composition and political areas of decision-making bodies had an influence on the type of policies designed to support care activities, both on the level of gender sensitivity of these policies and on the ability to take into account different categories of people (e.g., not regular workers, self-employed, single parents etc.)?
- How have civil society been engaged in the policy making? Has the absence of consultations with civil society had an impact on the type of policies designed to

support care activities?

- How have pre-pandemic policy mechanisms to ensure the integration of a gender perspective into policy making been affected by the pandemic and to what effects?
- What have been the best practices in place during the pandemic to support carers combining paid and unpaid work? Who have been the actors and what have been the effects?

The impact of societal initiatives during the pandemic on inequalities related to care responsibilities

There are several responses promoted by civil society within the domain of the gender care gap. Firstly, there are initiatives to support care activities for children and persons with disabilities. Different CSO's organised campaigns and lobbying activities to draw attention to, among other things, gender inequalities during the pandemic and the unsustainable burden of care work that is placed on the shoulders of women. Second, support for families has also come from initiatives aimed at delivering goods to those who couldn't move and at matching requests for services with voluntary work through online mutual aid platforms. Third, several organisations offered emotional and psychological support to people dealing with excessive stress because of the burden of combining care work and professional work. Initiatives were created to support education and thereby indirectly to support families by easing the burden of this work, for instance offering assistance to students from vulnerable groups with their homework. Finally, organisations also tried to alleviate the care burden of women by providing information about care activities, e.g., with online courses to support in the new care responsibilities created by the pandemic or through a guide for vulnerable groups about health-care centres and their rights.

However, there remains a research gap on the effects of civil society during crises such as COVID-19. Action oriented and participatory research approaches may support knowledge development around how and when gender norms and practices can be transformed and also be an important part of evidence-based innovations within the domain. Further research on the gender care gap should explore and develop innovations aiming to mitigate gender+ inequalities caused by policy responses to COVID-19. For this, the perspectives of underrepresented groups of women (migrants, refugees, people from LGBTQI+ communities), as well as men and children, need to be considered.

Knowledge Gaps and Research Questions Related to Work and Pay

Within RESISTIRÉ, the Work and Pay domain concerns itself with labour market issues, with particular focus on labour market inequalities such as the gender pay gap and the labour market gap, as well as the (gendered) experience of work, both formal and informal. This research found that some of the most affected target groups for this domain include women with care responsibilities, migrant women, domestic workers, elderly people with

low pensions, and in particular groups who lack access or capacity to use digital tools.

The gendered impact of teleworking

For those who were employed, many RAS found that women were more likely to work from home than men, or to have the opportunity to do so. Studies also indicated that working from home increased the number of hours in paid work and women were more likely to report poor or worsening work-life balance during the pandemic than men. Despite this, some studies indicated that women appreciated home working more than men and reported that their productivity increased. Indicating a debate about the effect of teleworking, there were also reports that productivity declined when working at home. Furthermore, although teleworking appears to have helped some women, particularly single mothers, to combine work and caring responsibilities, it is difficult to predict the long-term trend of hybrid working considering cultures of presenteeism in the workplace.

There is a need for more research on the impact of teleworking on productivity and work-life balance, since quantitative data has been inconclusive. Additionally, results indicate that teleworking leads to a disadvantage in terms of promotion, since promotions are biased towards those working in the office. Whether this penalty will remain once teleworking is more normalised, is yet to be seen. Furthermore, more research is also needed on whether the increased presence of fathers at home – because of telework – might affect gender-role attitudes, making them more egalitarian.

Research Questions:

- What are the consequences of teleworking on women's productivity, the household divisions of labour and mental health?
- Will women take up teleworking more than men in the future? How does the normalisation of telework impact inequalities such as the gender care gap and the promotion penalty in the long-term?
- How can telework contribute to more egalitarian relations and distribution of care work in the household?

The impact of the pandemic on the gender pay and pension gap

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a profound effect on Europe's economy, however there was a lack of comparable and harmonised data at a European level on the gender pay and pension gap. A few, localised RAS were mapped, but these could not be extrapolated at a wider European level. Given that women with low skills or educational attainment are more likely to be employed in precarious or informal working conditions (EIGE, 2017; ILO, 2018), it is likely these groups will be most affected. Additional research is needed to discern the long-term effects of the pandemic on the gender pay and pension gap, especially for women in vulnerable positions.

Research Questions:

- What is the long-term effect of the pandemic on the gender pay and pension gap, and, in particular, how are vulnerable groups impacted?

Policies in the domain of work and the overlooking of (gender) differences

In many countries, measures were gradually introduced to mitigate the effects of workplace closures, the need to stay at home, and rising unemployment, including: income support and compensation; job retention programmes; increased use of remote working, etc. However, such measures largely lacked a gender-sensitive lens and most of the policies excluded vulnerable workers such as atypical, informal and 'non-regular' workers. For instance, few policies or societal initiatives were mapped that related to the gender pay gap. A lack of investment was also noted in typically female-dominated sectors, such as health and health care facilities, which were overburdened with work during pandemic. This was reflected in qualitative indicators, where various groups of women stated they were not able to make use of universal and male-centred benefits.

Despite the support provided by governments through various welfare schemes (e.g., furlough), more attention should be paid in research to those who could not benefit from these policies, for instance because they were not formally employed. Additionally, findings from across the RESISTIRÉ project indicate that those who were already in vulnerable positions prior to the pandemic (e.g., migrants, refugees, self-employed, sex workers etc.) have been most affected, however data relating to these groups is most limited. Increased intersectional analysis would also be important here.

Research Questions:

- How has the pandemic affected those in non-formal or atypical employment? How do different inequality grounds lead to different experiences and outcomes for those in non-formal or atypical employment arrangements?

The vulnerability of women in the labour market is clear, but with sectoral differences

In the workshops, some experts reported women's working hours had increased, while others reported a reduction in women's employment. There was, however, consensus that variation is linked to sector-based differences: while some women's workload has increased (e.g., healthcare workers), women were generally vulnerable due to layoffs being concentrated among those with short-term contracts in female-dominated sectors. The variation in employment outcomes is also dependant on parental status. In particular, single mothers were found to be most affected due to COVID-19 and were at higher risk of poverty.

There is a research gap in regards to the effects of the pandemic on women's working patterns. Sector-based analysis will be important, as well as comparisons according to parent status.

Research Questions:

- How has the pandemic affected women's working patterns within different economic sectors?
- What has been the impact of women's family arrangements on these patterns?

Low pensions as a risks factor for women

While women's pensions may not have been directly affected by the pandemic, this research has found that in some cases elderly women received such low pensions that they had to work to receive additional income. As old age is a risk factor, the fear of contagion meant they were often unable to take on extra work during the pandemic.

The increased visibility of unpaid care work and its opportunities

There appears to have been some increased awareness of the importance of key workers in sectors like health and social care and thereby implicitly an increased awareness of the value of women's work. Researchers agree that one of the root causes of gender pay gap is the disproportionate amount of unpaid care work done by women. The increased visibility of care work in all its forms during the pandemic may have raised awareness of the value of women's contributions, but additional research is required.

Research Questions:

- To what extent has the pandemic lead to a re-evaluation of care work, and how could policies and/or societal initiatives reinforce and strengthen positive changes?

Knowledge Gaps and Research Questions Related to Human Rights and Health

Within the broader domain of human and fundamental rights, inequalities related to health and healthcare presented some of the most pressing knowledge gaps and research questions yet to be addressed, especially in light of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic and in terms of being prepared for any future health crises.

Gender+ inequalities in health and healthcare

Some groups are associated with far higher COVID-19 mortality rates than others. Older people stand out in this regard, but also ethnic minorities, which was put forward as evidence of an exacerbation of existing inequalities of these groups in access to healthcare. Social class affects not only access to healthcare (including access to private options and insurance) but also exposure to the virus: working-class people are more likely to work in high-risk settings.

Numerous RAS have reported a significant increase in mental health problems during the pandemic such as depression, anxiety, and sleeping problems among the general population, caused by such factors as social isolation, unemployment, financial strains,

uncertainties about the future, and work-life balance. In some countries, the impact on mental health was higher among women, and these differences were also found to be intersected with other vulnerabilities such as employment or parental status. Addressing this situation requires, among other factors, adequate access to mental healthcare, yet there is a notoriously high level of unmet need for mental health support in Europe (Alonso et al., 2007), and this will inevitably increase as a result of the pandemic, especially for the most vulnerable.

Women have unique (physical and mental) health needs, but at the same time they are less likely to have access to quality health services, such as medicines, vaccines or insurance coverage for health costs (UN, 2020). Before the pandemic, gender and socioeconomic inequalities in access to medical care were repeatedly reported in the literature, while during the crisis, the strain on hospitals and healthcare workers has led to a disruption of healthcare services and deferment of non-urgent care. This has led to a rise of unmet medical care needs that was not consistent across different population groups. For instance, Eurofound data showed that, in some EU countries, a higher proportion of women than men reported a rise in their unmet healthcare needs since the start of the pandemic. In our qualitative research, women also reported difficulties in accessing sexual and reproductive health services. Moreover, transgender women have been affected as gender reassignment surgery is considered elective and, therefore, postponed. People suffering from chronic illnesses, particularly older people, were also left more vulnerable.

Further analyses are needed to assess more systematically the extent to which the crisis has exacerbated such inequalities across Europe, especially in the intersection of multiple inequalities, such as ethnicity, socioeconomic status, disability, age, geographic location and sexual orientation. Eurostat data such as EU-SILC to be released at the end of 2021 would be useful in this endeavour as it will allow the use of harmonised data collected before and during/after the crisis. Still, some inequality grounds such as sexual orientation or some health outcomes such as sexual health needs cannot be examined using these Eurostat datasets.

Research Questions:

- What are the ways and policies to develop holistic healthcare based on an understanding of intersectionality and interdependence?
- How can primary and preventive healthcare services be strengthened in the face of future crises?
- Given the higher risks of delays in primary healthcare services for women, and especially for women with vulnerabilities, in which areas of healthcare have women disproportionately suffered negative consequences (e.g., cancer treatments, sexual health)?
- How can better quality access to women's healthcare be ensured in emergency contexts like future pandemics?
- How can access to transition-related healthcare and other care arrangements to

address the needs of LGBTQI+ people be ensured during crises like the COVID-19 pandemic?

- How are non-urgent medical procedures defined and what does this mean for treatments linked to transitions?

Vaccination and vaccine hesitancy

Inequalities in vaccination rates have been observed despite vaccines being available for free in most European countries: data are generally unavailable to assess inequalities in vaccination rates at the European level, yet some evidence exists at the national level. For instance, England shows a lower vaccination rate for people with lower socioeconomic status, poor English proficiency, and non-white ethnicity in the 50 and 70 plus age groups (Office for National Statistics, 2021). Some of the RAS indicated that women were more hesitant to get vaccinated against COVID-19, whereas older age and higher levels of education were factors that increased the willingness to take the vaccine. Given the ever-present threat of a new wave of the COVID-19 virus, it becomes crucial to better understand the patterns in inequalities in vaccination and vaccine hesitancy, the mechanisms behind these inequalities, and approaches to increase vaccination rates among at-risk and vulnerable groups. Promising ideas and practices to increase vaccination rates among people outside the healthcare system need to be examined and supported, such as vaccination programs that do not require identity documents.

Research Questions:

- How can vaccination inequalities be assessed at the European level?
- What are the underlying reasons behind inequalities in vaccination rates and how can they be addressed?
- What are some of the most promising practices and methods to increase vaccination rates and are they applicable on a large scale?

Links between access to care and other domains examined in RESISTIRÉ

Access to care also has some associations with other domains examined in this project. For instance, increasing care responsibilities of women at home during the crisis makes it difficult for them to allocate time for their own healthcare needs, including doctor visits. Unemployment and financial challenges, besides pandemic anxieties, have also added to minimizing the frequency of doctor visits for women. More research is needed to analyse the outcomes of this situation, including for women's sense of isolation and vulnerability in the face of gender-based violence. Indeed, women and LGBTQI+ victims and survivors of GBV, rely primarily on doctors, nurses and social workers for assistance rather than relying on police services, making this situation more challenging especially as the pressure placed upon shelters and charitable organisations exceed their capacity.

Research Questions:

- How can the needs of different societal groups be identified, with a focus on community health (rather than focusing on personal/individual healthcare)?
- How can policymakers be assisted in developing inclusive health policies?
- In what ways can new methodologies and participatory tools be developed to reach the most vulnerable groups in society?

Healthcare workers as new vulnerable group

Healthcare workers have suffered one of the heaviest burdens of the pandemic, as illustrated by the qualitative research. Among this group, a clear gender divide can be observed, as women held the majority of high-risk healthcare positions. Often, this higher risk for women is further accentuated by other characteristics. For instance, undocumented migrants working as care workers for chronic patients experience difficulties in accessing testing or COVID-related care due to fear of deportation. The absence of routines at the beginning of the pandemic, and the overworked staff throughout it (related to the general problem of understaffing in the healthcare sector), affected the quality of care. Narratives from both healthcare workers and patients show that understaffing in the healthcare sector meant there was no time for care in healthcare as staff struggled meet even the most basic needs of the patients. However, healthcare workers have learned a lot during the pandemic – lessons that are relevant for the domain of decision-making – and not taking the perspective of these health professionals into account might have severe costs in terms of future health crises and the desirability of the profession. It is therefore essential to reach out and consult with these groups to enhance preparedness for future crises.

Research Questions:

- What are the short- and long-term consequences of the gendered composition of (front-line) healthcare jobs?
- What can be done to prevent staff from becoming overworked and to make the profession more attractive?
- What mechanisms can be used to include healthcare workers more in decision-making processes and make sure that their first-hand experiences and ideas are genuinely taken into account?

Digital gaps and health literacy

According to RESISTIRÉ's qualitative research, increased digitalisation in healthcare has created barriers for population groups with limited digital means and literacy, such as older people, individuals with disabilities, migrants, Roma families, or more generally people with a lower socio-economic status. These groups might face difficulties in

accessing, understanding, appraising or using information on, for instance, how to prevent infection, how to get tested or vaccinated, how to build resilience, etc. These difficulties may be related to either a lack of means (e.g., a laptop or internet connection) or skills (e.g., language skills). It is therefore important to adapt the messages and tools related to the crisis to the literacy level and digital needs of the more vulnerable groups. Studies are needed to examine the adequacy between COVID-19 communications and health literacy levels, and develop initiatives to enhance this adequacy.

Research Questions:

- What are the short- and long-term consequences of increased healthcare digitalisation on the health of vulnerable groups?
- How can a digital divide in healthcare be prevented/reduced?

Knowledge Gaps and Research Questions Related to Gender-based Violence

Gender-based violence is violence directed towards a person because of their gender. It is rooted in gender inequality and continues to be one of the most widespread human rights violations within all societies. Both women and men experience gender-based violence but the majority of victims are women and girls. It is connected to power, capital, crime, economy, polity, and health. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, it has been estimated that one in three women will experience sexual or physical violence in their lifetime. This 'second' pandemic worsens during displacement and times of crisis; the threat of gender-based violence significantly increases for women and girls, and other already vulnerable groups, and is often accompanied by a reduction in support structures. However, during the COVID-19 crisis, the RESISITIRÉ findings – based analysis of policies, societal responses, expert interviews, expert workshops, and individual narrative interviews in 31 countries - show country variations in prevalence, reporting, help-seeking patterns and support structures, and their funding. These initial findings make the case for a need for more robust comparative evidence in the domain of gender-based violence in order to understand the impact of COVID-19 policies.

The crisis has intensified the problem of gender-based violence, but evidence of prevalence and reporting are unclear and contradictory

The findings from the first cycle research include that since the outbreak of COVID-19, emerging data and reports from frontliners suggest an intensification in and/or transformation of gender-based violence, in particularly (men's) violence against women and girls, including domestic violence, sexual violence and online violence and abuse, and violence against already vulnerable groups such as LGBTQI people and 65+ people. There are indications of increases in violence from intimate partners and of decreases in violence from non-partners - meaning that violence has increased when women are isolated at

home with their partners, but decreased in other places (e.g., work) where there is less contact. This raises the need to explore the notion of home as a place of safety, which has formed the basis for policy on isolation and/or confinement in the home, since it neglects and worsens the situation of victims/survivors of multiple forms of gender-based violence in the home.

Evidence also suggests that these increases and intensifications continue to strain health services and other essential services, such as domestic violence shelters and helplines. In some countries, the state and/or public authorities have ear-marked funding for the NGO sector to increase its capacity to support victims of gender-based violence.

Simultaneously however, administrative and official data provided by public authorities show no change in the prevalence of gender-based violence or the intensity compared to prior the pandemic. The quantitative data on gender-based violence during the pandemic is thus contradictory: official administrative data show one thing, while reports provided by frontlines and NGOs offering legal, social, and psychological support to victims, show another.

The overall research gap thus concerns the immediate effects of the crisis on prevalence and women's and vulnerable groups safety. To address this gap, harmonised comparative data are needed. Findings on gender-based violence are contradictory and unclear, with increases in some contexts of the crisis and decreases in others: more harmonised quantitative data at the European level, and substantial European level research to address and analyse gender-based violence are needed. Data collection on gender-based violence should specifically include violence against LGBTQI; and when possible, distinguish between violence against lesbians, gay, trans, queer, and intersex: these groups may not experience the same levels of violence and vulnerability, but still tend to be grouped together as one. Further, the definition of domestic violence should be expanded to include violence of family members towards LGBTIQ+ people to be able to develop more inclusive preventive measures and policies in the face of a new crisis.

Research Questions:

- Why are there discrepancies in the findings between official data and reports from frontline actors? What are the causes of these discrepancies?
- What is the change in prevalence of gender-based violence during the crisis? With what consequences in terms of health and well-being?
- Are there increase or decreases in specific forms of violence? Are there new, emerging forms of violence, violations and abuse, due to different degrees of isolation, and to increased online presence?
- To what extent and which policies are functional to or constitute forms of GBV themselves (including psychological and economic violence)?
- These questions need to be addressed comparatively and by asking questions both

about life-time prevalence and in the last year.

New forms and increased visibility of existing forms of gender-based violence: challenging the safety of the home and witnessing a re-traditionalisation of gender roles

Evidence suggests that new visibility of certain forms of violence have emerged as a consequence of isolation and the shift towards digital work and education, in particular new forms of online violence and abuse, and better visibility of forms of violence related to the home as a place of safety for women and children, and LGBTQI people. The shift to online/digital work and education have enabled increased, sometime new forms of violence and abuse as monitoring and control. Studies also show that domestic violence against young women and LGBTQI+, who returned to their family homes, during the pandemic have increased. What emerges here is a form of re-traditionalisation of gender roles, which is monitored and controlled via online monitoring and policing, as an emerging form of violence - stretching its meaning beyond physicality and focusing on the experiences of the victim/survivor.

The RESISTIRÉ primary qualitative data show far-reaching effects of the crisis on gender-based violence related inequalities, in particular violence against young people and violence against LGBTQI people, in the context of new forms of online violence and abuse, by acquaintances as well as family members. Lockdowns and isolation have challenged the idea of the home as safe, not least by LGBTQI persons who have been forced to come out while staying at home.

Research Questions:

- Are there new, emerging forms of gender-based violence, violations and abuse? How do these relate to the notion of 'home' as a safe place? Under what conditions can the home be considered as a place of safety for women, girls, young people and LGBTQI people?
- What are the new, emerging forms of violence, violations and abuse, derived from isolation, lockdowns, and digitalisation? While the internet has expanded communication capacities, it has also become a site of violence and a tool to facilitate violence, gender-based hate speech, and crimes. What are the new forms, and with what effects for different groups and inequalities?
- How are these new forms, and increased visibility of existing forms, related to the shift from offline to online work and education?
- What are the impacts on specific inequality groups (e.g., women, girls, young people, older people, LGBTQI+ people)?
- Are patterns of differences or similarities between countries, related to the degree of lockdown, isolation, and resilience of the gender equality structure/institutions?

The effects of the crisis on women's and vulnerable groups' security and the role of the state versus civil society

While the evidence on the effects of the pandemic on women's and girls' and vulnerable groups' safety is mixed (see above), the evidence on security via reporting and access to the criminal justice system point in the same direction: many sources consulted during the first cycle mapping show that women were unlikely to report violence and abuse to the authorities and unlikely to tell anyone about their experiences of gender-based violence. If they did, they were more likely to seek psychological care from their GPs rather than assistance from the police.

The removal of access to escape routes, whether to friends, family, or alternative accommodations in shelters introduce obstacles for women and other vulnerable groups to gain information about and access to these services. Moreover, women with low digital literacy or a lack of access to digital tools were reported to be vulnerable since they could not make use of digital solutions for contacting services without being overheard or leaving traces. Such tools exclude those who do not access to devices and networks, and those who do not have the skills to use existing devices or networks. Safety from gender-based violence thus relate to knowledge and access to digital tools.

Simultaneously, there has been an increased need for assistance, increased pressure on shelters, and an increase in help seeking from civil societal organisations. Thus, the reporting to the police of gender-based violence during the crisis has decreased, while the use of health services and civil society organisations have increased.

Such shift means an increased pressure on volunteer groups, and decreased pressure on the state funded criminal justice system. It also means that victims may receive less support and access to resources.

Civil society and NGOs are positioned differently in different countries, with state support enabling the sector to mobilise and support victims of GBV in some countries, whereas in others, the mobilising of NGOs support during the crisis has been enabled through other mechanisms. The conditions under which NGOs are able to mobilise and provide support to victims of GBV during crisis need to be further examined and compared.

Research Questions:

- Has there been a decrease in reporting, handling of cases or sentencing (or variations in punishment)? And if so, why?
- How can reporting of violence and abuse be facilitated/increased? How can women and vulnerable groups access digital help-seeking and support tools? What are the opportunities and constraints? Are new tools needed, or is it an issue of equal 'digital literacy'?
- How have digitalisation and digital ill/literacy effected victims' capacity to report and

authorities' powers to intervene? On the one hand, tools to access services have turned digital to overcome physical/social restrictions and ensure access to support services and mechanisms. Digital solutions (WhatsApp, apps with geo-location, etc.) allowed contacting services without being overheard or leaving traces. On the other hand, all do not have the digital literacy to make use of such tools.

- How can civil society be better equipped to address the need of support of victims, in particular the support needed during lockdowns, and taking the shifting forms of violence and abuse, with a focus on different inequality groups, into account?
- The pandemic has created a particular set of challenges to the provision of services for victims/survivors of gender-based violence and reinforced the need to develop flexible and resilient systems of response and support. Under what conditions do these work, or not? Which systems have responded well to the new challenges posed by the pandemic? What made these systems more sustainable, more resilient in the face of a new crisis?
- What is the role and possible capacity of bystanders to gender-based violence (colleagues, neighbours, friends)

The voices of and support to the most vulnerable

There is significant evidence that the most vulnerable were made even more vulnerable to gender-based violence during the crisis. The civil society sector has often stepped in to meet the different rights and needs of these groups, groups often left out of policy and mainstream societal processes and organising: public responses have primarily targeted mainstream women, and services and public policies have been unable to address gender-based violence intersectionally. This has meant that violence from family members (fathers, brothers, and sometimes mothers) is usually not considered, and that support mechanisms are mostly designed for married heterosexual women with children. The often excluded and multiply vulnerable groups include marginalised and disadvantaged groups such as LGBTQI+ victims of gender-based violence, +65 victims of gender-based violence, homeless victims of gender-based violence, ROMA victims of gender-based violence, and refugee victims of gender-based violence. Further, the situation of girls/women in trafficking and/or prostitution has been severely worsened during the crisis: trafficked girls have stayed with their exploiters as they had no home, women in prostitution were forced to work without any security measures; et cetera.

Research Questions:

- How do different polities/political systems include/exclude the voices and interests of the most marginalised in policy-making on gender-based violence? Are different systems better or worse; how, why?
- Comparative policy analysis of policymaking in times of crises: there is a lack of research that examine the effects of policy and the policymaking process on prevalence for

different groups; research should contrast and compare policy-making on gender-based violence from an intersectional perspective, both across countries and across different crises within countries. Ultimately, such research would help further understand what policy could help reduce gender-based violence in times of crises.

Research Agenda for Cycle 2

Findings and gaps identified in the first research cycle

The first cycle of analysis shows that national policy and societal responses are unequally (un)able to address gender+ inequalities, despite decades of gender mainstreaming in EU policymaking. Furthermore, quantitative as well as qualitative indicators expose an increase in existing and new, emerging, inequalities, where some groups have been made vulnerable to a higher extent than others.

Findings and gaps identified by research on policies and societal responses

The first cycle policy mapping collected qualitative information on policies and societal responses at the national and regional levels that allow us to analyze the impact on the economic, social and environmental impacts of COVID-19. The aim was to describe and analyse the gender dimensions and impacts of policies and societal responses implemented in Europe in the course of and in relation to the COVID-19 pandemic.

The primary data were generated by 29 national researchers in the EU27 countries (excluding Estonia and Malta) along with Iceland, Serbia, Turkey, and the UK. The mapping showed that most policies introduced to manage the pandemic did not take gendered and intersectional inequalities, including e.g., gender and gender identity, nationality, migration, and age. This lack was especially pronounced in, but not limited to, the first phase of the pandemic. Among the eight domains, gender-based violence is the one with the most pronounced gender perspective. The second concerns work and pay. However, such measures have often targeted particular sectors and segments of the population, the more 'regular' ones, leaving specific groups of people and, in particular, women in a difficult position.

Although the pandemic has made the difficulties of care work more evident, little has been done to prevent the burden of this work falling mainly on women. While in some cases there has been a greater sensitivity to the need to support more affected groups, such as single mothers and people with disabilities, most of these measures have been gender blind and have failed to address intersecting inequalities. The need to legislate on issues such as the movement of people, the closure of schools and services for education, and the management of health-care services had substantial implications for the enactment and protection of human and fundamental rights. COVID-related policies have often been supplemented with as well as counteracted by initiatives introduced by civil society organisations to combat these inequalities. Some groups have focused on collecting and analysing data to shed light on inequalities, while others have concentrated on awareness-

raising and protest campaigns relating to the rights of different vulnerable groups. The forms of these initiatives have ranged from offering concrete support through the distribution of essential goods and providing shelter to creating mutual aid platforms to help meet the demand for and supply of goods and services. Many materials with information were produced and distributed to people in need whom official information channels often do not reach. Civil society organisations have also offered health and psychological assistance to people in need.

An analysis of the national reports and of the diversity of the policies that were mapped shows that the priority for policymakers, especially during the first phase of the pandemic, was to balance the protection of public health with maintaining economic production. In several cases, the national researchers pointed out that policies were underpinned by an implicit representation of society as cisgender and made up of 'traditional' and 'regular' families (where people have citizenship and standard employment contracts) with two parents and one or two children. In this layout and within the mapped policies, women were regarded as primarily responsible for unpaid care activities but also for performing essential jobs such as healthcare workers, domestic workers, cashiers etc.

Findings and gaps identified by quantitative research

The first cycle quantitative research collected comparative information on indicators that allow us to measure and monitor the economic, social and environmental impacts of COVID-19. Two types of mappings were conducted, providing us with both European and national level insights on the impact of COVID-19. The first mapping (European insights) looked at official secondary data sources at international and EU levels, while the second mapping (national insights) concerned Rapid Assessment Surveys (RAS), that is, studies conducted on the initiative of lobby groups, scientists or official agencies that provide fast, research-based assessments. The aim of the first analysis was to provide analytical insights before the outbreak to identify baseline levels and compare these with data collected during the pandemic. It also sets the baseline for cycles two and three of the project, which will delve deeper into the issues highlighted in this first cycle, and review and investigate the evolution of inequalities throughout the COVID-19 pandemic.

While evidence provided a clear picture of some aspects of inequalities in Europe, a detailed analysis was not possible for all domains due to data availability. In particular, comparable and harmonised data at a European level is needed on the gender pay gap, gender-based violence, decision making and environmental justice. Importantly, existing data is particularly limited for the most marginalised groups in society and current analyses rarely extend beyond differences in socioeconomic status, family structure and education. Non-registered workers, migrants, refugees and the homeless are likely to have been severely affected by COVID-19 and related government restrictions, however little evidence is available to assess these implications across the domains of interest. There is an urgent need for European databases to take varied inequality grounds into consideration to better understand the economic, social and environmental impacts of COVID-19 related policies through a gender+ lens. Local rapid assessment surveys,

providing fast, research-based assessments, have proved useful for filling some these gaps and offer an insight into issues at national level. However, further data and/or better integration of existing data is needed, especially at a European level.

Findings and gaps identified by qualitative research

The first cycle qualitative research collected information on indications that allow us to analyse economic, social and environmental inequalities within the framework developed in RESISTIRÉ. It included eight pan-European workshops with inequality experts from civil society representing the voices of specific target groups, public authority experts and academics (n=68); semi-structured interviews with predominantly public authority experts and academics (n=23); and via individual narratives interviews with people from across Europe (n=188).

The overall findings of this first cycle of qualitative data describe a complex picture, where different groups of women remain significantly disadvantaged across all domains and where there is spiral of increasing inequalities; being marginalised or disadvantaged makes you disproportionately vulnerable to further disadvantaged or marginalisation. COVID-19 and its policy responses have made the most vulnerable even more vulnerable, particularly in strong gender regimes where social class, migrant status, and age regimes cut straight across domains. These findings suggest an inter-relation between domains and intersections between inequalities.

Changes in inequalities and gender relations in one domain, whether due to the pandemic itself or its policy and (civil) societal responses, are interlinked with changes in other domains – these appear to take each other as ‘environments’. While there are many similarities in the findings, the differences that detected in how the pandemic unfolds on macro, meso and micro levels indicate variations in terms of system resilience that can account for these variations. The results furthermore indicate that the mechanisms that enable resilience are different on the different levels. The individual experiences analysed show that while there certainly are stories of extreme marginalisation, exhaustion, and devastation in the lives of women across Europe, there are better stories with the potential for transformative change at the micro level, which may indeed be picked up by or spill over to the meso level, if supported by the macro level. Knowledge gaps to address in the second cycle

The above-mentioned insights from the first cycle, call for second cycle attention on factors impacting the possibility for a fair and equal recovery, towards resilience and social justice.

In the second cycle, a specific focus will be to continue to investigate in-depth the domains particularly affected by the pandemic. Particular attention will be paid to the unintended consequences of policy and societal responses, and to the ways forward in terms of better stories (that is, inspiring and promising practices).

Table 4 - Second Cycle Research Focus of the Three Research Work Packages

Focus/data collection	Quantitative indicators (WP3)	Policy and societal responses (WP2)	Qualitative indications (WP4)
Domains	All but particular attention to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Care Human and fundamental rights Gender-based violence Work and pay 	All but particular attention to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Care Decision-making Gender-based violence Work and pay 	Particular attention to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Care (interviews/narratives) Gender-based violence (WS/interviews/narratives) Education (WS/interviews/narratives) Work and Pay (WS/interviews/narratives)
Recovery	RAS, EU secondary data analysis	Recovery plans and policy	WS/interviews/narratives
Unintended consequences	RAS, EU secondary data analysis	Recovery plans and policy	WS/interviews/narratives
Better stories	RAS, EU secondary data analysis	Recovery plans and policy	WS/interviews/narratives
Gender+ data/intersectional analysis	RAS, EU secondary data analysis	Recovery plans and policy	WS/interviews/narratives
Resilience of gender equality systems and mechanisms for gender mainstreaming	RAS, EU secondary data analysis	Recovery plans and policy	WS/interviews/narratives

Cross-cutting research themes

A main conclusion from the first research cycle is the need to dig deeper into specific questions. While the first cycle enabled a generic scoping and wide data collection, the second cycle allows for a more focused approach, in order to dig deeper into some of the most salient inequalities touched upon in the first cycle. To facilitate depth over range, the research in the second cycle will therefore reduce the number of domains in focus, and

ensure the inclusion of specifically vulnerable groups that were not given sufficient voice in the first cycle, including LGBTQI+, migrants, Roma, and 65+, from a gender+ perspective. Across all eight domains, five crosscutting research themes will guide the research and analysis in the second cycle: 1) recovery, 2) better stories, 3) gender+ data and intersectional analysis, 4) the resilience of gender equality systems and 5) the mechanisms for gender mainstreaming in times of crisis. Additionally, the RESISTIRÉ Advisory Board, which supports the project with their expertise, initiated the idea of a research theme on vaccination and inequalities and reasons related thereto.

Recovery

Based on the findings of the first cycle, and especially in relation to the overall lack of an integration of gender+ equality perspective in pandemic policy responses (including a lack of gender+ data and gender+ expertise in the policy process), there is a particular need in the second cycle to focus on the overall recovery politics, and the specific recovery policies. Research questions/focus:

Policies and societal responses

- How are gender + inequalities integrated into recovery plans initiatives to mitigate the effects from pandemic policymaking?
- How have civil society organizations contributed to the design of these recovery plans and policies and/or how are they responding to these measures?
- What are the potential effects from the findings?

Quantitative indicators

- Are gender+ data available for integration analysis in recovery plans on national and European levels?

Qualitative indications

- Which inequality grounds are taken into considerations in recovery plans and which are missing?
- What are the main obstacles for integrating gender+ perspectives in ongoing/future pandemic responses (including recovery plans)?
- What are the main effects on individuals from ongoing/future pandemic responses (including recovery plans)?

Better stories

Within RESISTIRÉ, we identify “Better Stories”, a term taken from Dina Georgis (2013) for promising practices that identify how a given societal situation can be ameliorated to improve existing practices. From the findings of the first cycle, it is clear that there are many important contributions and innovative responses, not least from civil societal actors and feminist activists. There is an overall need to continue to collect and learn from these

initiatives, in particular to develop an understanding of why and under which circumstances, some initiatives seem successful whereas others are regarded as failures. More research is needed into the long-term effects of initiatives and their applicability in different contexts. The focus on better stories here is relevant for all other crosscutting themes and the domains. Research questions/focus include:

Policies and societal responses

- What better stories can be detected in recovery plans and policies, and what makes these initiative a better story?
- What better stories can be identified in the processes of involvement of civil society organisations in the design of the recovery plans and policies?

Quantitative indicators

- What better stories can be detected in data collected on a national and European level and why?

Qualitative indications

- What better stories are voiced, experienced or found in the narratives, and what makes these better stories?

Unintended consequences

The unintended consequences of the COVID-19 policy and societal responses are an underlying focus in RESISTIRÉ. For the second research cycle however, we intend to bring this silent focus to the analytical fore, by explicitly asking questions about the unintended consequences.

Policies and societal responses

- Do recovery plans and policies take into account unexpected consequences related to gender+ inequalities that emerged and were identified during the early stages of the pandemic?
- During the design of the recovery plans and policies, have the policy makers used any tools to prevent the emergence of unintended consequences (e.g. Gender Impact Assessment)?

Quantitative indicators

- To what extent is quantitative gender+ data available that can indicate potential unintended consequences of COVID-19 policy on national and European levels? What are the main data gaps?

Qualitative indications

- To what extent are unintended consequences experienced on the individual level, and how are these experienced by different inequality groups?

Integrating gender+ and intersectionality into the data collection and analysis

Existing data is particularly limited for the most marginalised groups in society and current analyses rarely extend beyond differences in socioeconomic status, family structure and education. Non-registered workers, migrants, refugees and the homeless are likely to have been severely affected by COVID-19 and related government restrictions, however little evidence is available to assess these implications across the domains of interest. Furthermore, although gender or sex variables were included in most national Rapid Assessment Surveys (RAS), analysis from a gender perspective was lacking in the reported findings. The reports by NRs showed that the design of policies to respond to the pandemic in Europe in many cases lacked a gender+ sensitivity, even if some exceptions are present. The qualitative findings shows that the fact that a gender + perspective was not taken into account in policy making had severe and unequal effects on how individuals are able to cope with the pandemic. There is an urgent need for European databases to take varied inequality grounds into consideration to better understand the economic, social and environmental impacts of COVID-19 related policies through a gender+ lens. Further data and/or better integration of existing data is needed, especially at a European level. The gap will be further investigated in the second research cycle. Research questions/focus:

Policies and societal responses

- Particular attention will be on when and why gender+ data is collected and/or used in policy making and on the role of civil society in the use of gender+ data

Quantitative indicators

- In order to understand gaps in gender+ data better, specific questions on methodology applied by national researchers in the first cycle will be addressed, including:
 1. the search process for the RAS;
 2. the rationale for inclusion for each RAS;
 3. an overview of what was missing among the RAS; and
 4. the rationale for selection of promising RAS .
- Opportunities for collaboration with RAS authors will be investigated alongside European data collection via a RESISTIRÉ phone-based app to address gaps in data and incorporate gender + analysis. This could focus particularly on the domains and inequality grounds where comparable data was limited in cycle 1.
- A gender+ and intersectionality lens will be applied to EU secondary data analysis to enhance understanding and address a research gap - identified in the first cycle - of intersecting inequalities, e.g., interest groups who have been specifically vulnerable to the impact of the crisis, including, but not limited to single parents, migrants, LGBTQI, and youth.

Qualitative indications

- Specific focus will be paid to understand the effects of lack of gender+ data and intersectional policy analysis on individual lives in the analysis of the data collected through workshops, interviews and in the narratives
- In the narratives particular attention is paid to those vulnerable groups that were less represented in the collection in the first research cycle. Particular attention will be paid to; young persons, LGBTQI people, migrants, refugees, 65+ persons, victims/survivors or bystanders of gender-based violence. The collection will include women, men, and non-binary persons.

The resilience of gender equality systems and mechanisms for gender mainstreaming in times of crisis

The effects on individuals and individual behavioural and social and economic inequality of the pandemic and its policy responses can be seen as a test of the resilience of the existing gender equality institutions and mechanisms in a given geo-political context. Despite the fact that gender mainstreaming has been adopted as an approach in EU policymaking for over two decades, we continue to see that policies are in fact largely not mainstreamed at the national level.

The mapping show that most of the policies that were introduced to manage the pandemic did not take into account aspects related to gender inequalities and other intersecting vulnerability grounds, such as gender identity, nationality, and age. This lack was especially pronounced in but not limited to the first phase of the pandemic. In the second cycle specific attention will be directed to understanding the resilience of gender equality systems and mechanisms for gender mainstreaming in times of crisis. Research needs to address resilience aspects on various levels of gender equality governance as well as the interdependency of macro, meso and micro levels to understand the effects on gender equality. The aim is to enable learning and development to build stronger gender equality systems to increase system readiness in times of crisis. Research questions/focus:

Policies and societal responses

- How has the gender composition of decision-makers and scientific and technical committees affected the gender sensitivity of the policies that have been adopted?
- Does the gender of the decision-makers make a difference?
- What have been the role of civil society, e.g., gender+ NGOs, in policy making?

Quantitative indicators

- How have datasets developed to monitor gender+ inequalities (both as part of regular and extraordinary monitoring) been affected in times of crisis?

Qualitative indications

- How is the resilience of gender equality system (including mechanisms for gender mainstreaming) affected in times of crisis?
- Which actors are involved on the different levels? Are these actors the same or different pre/during and post-pandemic?
- How are the experiences of citizens are accounted for and incorporated into policy making?

Domain-based research questions

In cycle 2 all domains are addressed but the focus has shifted to those that were more prominent or lacking in data in cycle 1. Below are the domains and research questions that will be in specific focus during cycle 2.

Care

Specific attention will be paid to the Care domain in Cycle 2 in all work-packages. Research questions/focus:

Policies and societal responses

- What consideration has been given to gender+ care-gap issues within national policies aimed at socio-economic recovery from the pandemic (especially with regard to the National Recovery and Resilience Plan instrument)?
- What role have civil society organisations had in the design processes of these plans and their reactions on both contents and processes?

Quantitative indicators

- What intersecting inequalities, relating to e.g. race/ethnicity, nationality, household composition, sexuality and gender identity can be identified within gender care gaps, through analysis of European level data and utilisation of national RAS?

Qualitative indications

- What role does care play in relation to recovery during the COVID-19-pandemic?
- In which ways are care, as a means of recovery, expressed in governmental policies, CSO responses and individuals' narratives?

Work and pay

Specific attention will be paid to the Work & Pay domain in Cycle 2 in all work-packages. Research questions/focus:

Policies and societal responses

- Have labour-related measures in recovery plans and policies taken into account how the pandemic has affected women and vulnerable groups differently?
- Have trade unions and employers' organizations been involved in the design of the policies? How are they responding to the plans?

Quantitative indicators

- What intersecting inequalities, relating to e.g. race/ethnicity, nationality, household composition, sexuality and gender identity can be identified within labour market and pay gaps, through analysis of European level data and utilisation of national RAS?

Qualitative indications

- How have inequalities relating to the work & pay gap domain been informing recovery strategies and why?
- What effects have pandemic responses and recovery strategies had on individual lives in terms of work opportunities, working conditions and equal pay?

Gender-based violence

Specific attention will be paid to the GBV domain in Cycle 2 in all work-packages. Research questions/focus:

Policies and societal responses

- What consideration has been given to the need to strengthen the support to the victims of GBV and the collaboration with CSOs (that become more evident during the phases of home confinement) within national recovery plans and policies?
- How have inequalities relating to gender-based violence informed recovery strategies and why?

Quantitative indicators

- What intersecting inequalities, relating to e.g. race/ethnicity, nationality, sexuality and gender identity can be identified within gender-based violence (e.g. isolation and lockdown effects), through analysis of European level data and utilisation of national RAS?

Qualitative indications

- What effects have pandemic responses and recovery strategies had for individuals in relation to gender-based violence?
- How have isolation and lockdown affected the experiences of different forms of violence, e.g., physical violence vs coercion and control, and online violence? and more coercion and surveillance and control?
- What is the role of technology in the emerging forms of gender-based violence during lockdown?

Human and fundamental rights: Education and Environmental Justice

Environmental Justice is a specific focus in WP2 and Education is especially addressed in WP4 where education is understood broadly and can include individuals' experiences of education in various settings and educational systems (from preschool services to higher education, online/offline settings, the state/local authorities/companies/NGOs etc.).

Research questions/focus:

Policies and societal responses

- How have inequalities relating to the education focus of the domain been informing recovery strategies and why?
- What is the role/voice/visibility of pupils, students, and others in education in the recovery plans and policy?
- Does the recovery plans and policies contain actions to mitigate gender+ inequalities in relation to the availability of green spaces to support people's health and well-being?

Quantitative indicators

- What intersecting inequalities, relating to e.g. race/ethnicity, nationality, household composition, sexuality and gender identity can be identified in relation to the environment and education, through analysis of European level data and utilisation of national RAS?

Qualitative indications

- What effects have pandemic responses and recovery strategies had on individual lives in terms of education?

Decision-making

Decision-making is a particular focus in WP2. Research questions/focus:

Policies and societal responses

- Is it possible to identify any connections between the composition of the decision-making bodies and the level of gender+ sensitivity of the recovery plans and policies?
- What was the level of involvement of civil society, and in particular of organisations related to gender+ inequalities, in the design processes of recovery plans and policies?

Qualitative indications

- Is there any reference to decision-making in the narratives? If so, is this gendered?
- Are there any patterns in the narratives in terms of voicing and experiencing inequalities and the gendered composition of the counties' decision-making bodies?

Conclusions

This report provides an overview of the Operational Recommendations, Pilot Projects and Research Agendas that have been developed as part of WP6. It is an important milestone for the project as these are the operational results of the first cycle. Concretely, the output consists of eight Operational Recommendations and three Pilot Projects, in addition to four thematic Research Agendas and one Research Agenda for RESISTIRÉ's second cycle.

The production of these outputs has followed different processes for the recommendations, the pilot projects and the research agenda, which have worked quite well overall through a spontaneous distribution of work among the partners, often triggered by motivation to work on the subject. One of the main lessons learned therefore is that the agreed processes, with both internal and external checks, has worked. Still, improvements are possible and lessons have been learned for implementation in the next cycles.

Another one of these lessons is anticipation. This is more feasible for the recommendations and for the research agenda. The identification of subjects and priorities can be started during the analysis phase of WP2, 3 and 4, and does not have to wait till the results of the open studios are available. Four of the eight recommendations are based on research results with marginal input from the open studios (as the themes were not covered in the open studios). The open studios have provided input for the research agenda, but defining the structure was done without direct input.

A third lesson is the importance of visuals to strengthen the messages. This is particularly true for the recommendations that will be promoted widely. The decision to invest in visually supporting the messages with charts and infographics was a consequence of the workshop held on the 10th of November. Images are enhancing messages and carriers of cultural values. As many of the themes covered in RESISTIRÉ are sensitive, it is important to make the right choices and to find the right balance. We discovered we can still learn and improve in this respect and will introduce capacity-building, mutual exchanges of experiences and expertise and more checks and balances in the process.

Finally, the use of the concept of "better stories" could also be implemented in the development of these first outputs of the project. The RESISTIRÉ team decided to use the concept when preparing the first cycle of open studios. It is now becoming like a 'red threat' for the project. The positiveness of the concept helps to keep the focus on solutions and on the ambition to change for better in a context where the reality and the facts are often depressing.

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